

APPARENT COLORS OF 2D MATERIALS

Sergio Puebla^{1,*}, Hai Li², Hua Zhang^{3,4,5}, Andres Castellanos-Gomez^{1,*}

- 1 *Materials Science Factory, Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Madrid (ICMM), Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), Sor Juana Inés de la Cruz 3, 28049 Madrid, Spain.*
- 2 *Key Laboratory of Flexible Electronics (KLOFE) & Institute of Advanced Materials, Nanjing Tech University, Nanjing, 211816, China*
- 3 *Department of Chemistry, City University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong, China*
- 4 *Hong Kong Branch of National Precious Metals Material Engineering Research Center (NPMM), City University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong, China*
- 5 *Shenzhen Research Institute, City University of Hong Kong, Shenzhen, 518057, China*

*Corresponding authors' e-mail: Sergio.puebla@csic.es, Andres.castellanos@csic.es

Keywords: Thin films, Apparent color, Optical Contrast, two-dimensional materials, flake, SiO₂.

Finding 2D and thin films layered materials has become essential in order to develop not only in scientific-related fields, but also in a wide industry, which is constantly feeding from this progress. For electronic devices, thin films materials have supposed to be a step forward to overcome the Moore's law. In many other technologic areas, the development of tools based on flake of materials has found new physics, becoming a rising field. Although, destructive techniques are commonly used to characterize the thickness of these materials. In this review, we present a list of materials, which thicknesses have been characterized by their apparent colors in several substrates; a harmless, fast and reliable technique that has been already used to determine the number of layers in several works. We also enlarge this list with other materials and substrates.

1. Introduction

The production of two-dimensional (2D) materials through mechanical exfoliation is rather straightforward. In fact, it is likely that single-layer thick flakes of different 2D materials were isolated even before the seminal paper of Novoselov and Geim published in 2004^[1]. Then why 2D materials research did not bloom until 2004? Even though the production of ultrathin materials by mechanical exfoliation was not an issue, finding these flakes and discriminating them from bulky flakes was an unsolved challenge until 2004. Indeed, mechanical exfoliation produces a random assortment of flakes with different thicknesses, lateral dimensions and shapes deposited on the surface of acceptor substrate. Therefore, the development of easy, fast, high-throughput and non-destructive techniques to identify ultrathin flakes of 2D materials and distinguish them from thick flakes was the inflection point for the rapid growth of this research field.

Optical microscopy-based methods have been proven to be the most suited ones to rapidly identify atomically thin 2D materials flakes^[2–6]. Nowadays there are methods based on Raman spectroscopy, photoluminescence, micro-transmittance/reflectance, Rayleigh scattering, or optical path interferometry that allow the accurate thickness determination of a wide range of 2D materials. Nonetheless, these more sophisticated optical microscopy-based methods are always preceded by a coarse thickness estimation based on the apparent color of the flakes. That is, flakes of different thicknesses have different apparent colors due to a combination of optical absorption and interference color effect. This thickness-dependent color can be further enhanced by depositing the 2D materials flakes on top of specific substrates that optimize the interference color effect. Despite the relevance of the coarse thickness estimation through the observation of their apparent color, a comprehensive summary of the reported color vs. thickness datasets is lacking in the literature. This is the goal of this work, to gather this information in a single article,

unifying the format of the presented datasets to facilitate the reader finding the necessary information. We believe that this work will become particularly useful for those researchers starting to work on a new 2D material family. Furthermore, we have added new figures of different materials, by delaminating them using scotch-tape method and placing them on several substrates using deterministic transfer methods^[7], to complement the data that are already published.

The thickness-dependent apparent color of 2D materials can be explained in the basis of a multiple-media optical system (see Figure 1(a)), in which the incident light reaches a surface, that it could be the substrate or the flake, and it crosses every media until reaching the Si wafer. At this point the light comes back along the same path (we suppose normal incidence) and reaches the measuring device. The light reflected or transmitted by this system can be calculated by applying the Fresnel law^[8] at each interface and considering the attenuation and the phase shift introduced while the different light beams propagate along each media. The reflected intensity for monochromatic light at a normal incidence is written following the Eq. (1)^[9].

$$I = \frac{r_{01}e^{i(\phi_1+\phi_2)}+r_{12}e^{-i(\phi_1-\phi_2)}+r_{23}e^{-i(\phi_1+\phi_2)}+r_{01}r_{12}r_{23}e^{i(\phi_1-\phi_2)}}{e^{i(\phi_1+\phi_2)}+r_{01}r_{12}e^{-i(\phi_1-\phi_2)}+r_{01}r_{23}e^{-i(\phi_1+\phi_2)}+r_{12}r_{23}e^{i(\phi_1-\phi_2)}} \quad (1)$$

Where the reflection coefficient is $r_{ij}=(n_i-n_j)/(n_i+n_j)$, the phase shift in the medium i is $\Phi_i = 2\pi n_i d_i/\lambda$, n_i is its respective complex refractive index, d_i is its thickness and λ is the wavelength. The subindexes 0, 1, 2 and 3 are assigned as air, flake, SiO₂ and Si, respectively.

The Optical Contrast (C) is defined in the Eq. (2) and it can be experimentally obtained using an experimental system as it is explained by Frisenda R. et al^[10].

$$C = \frac{I_f - I_s}{I_f + I_s} \quad (2)$$

Being I_f the reflected intensity acquired on the flake, and I_s the intensity acquired on the substrate, I_f can be obtained using the Eq. (1) and I_s can be determined replacing the flake for air in the medium 1. Figure 1(b) shows an example of how the C changes by using different flake thicknesses from 5 nm to 93 nm. It has been obtained by using values of air as a first medium, with a refractive index $n_0=1$; a substrate thickness of $d_1=297$ nm of SiO_2 , with a refractive index $n_1=1.5$; and a semi-infinite Si media with a refractive index that is dependent on the wavelength.

Figure 1. (a) Physical model of the system used to calculate the optical contrast. (b) C obtained with the parameters shown in the dashed line box for several values of the flake thickness. Adapted from [4].

This method has been seen in several previous works that use silicon substrates with a top SiO_2 layer of specific thicknesses, yielding a strong thickness dependence of the 2D materials apparent colors^[2-4], and thus facilitating their optical identification. The most extended substrates are SiO_2/Si with thickness of SiO_2 layer in the range of 70-90 nm or

270-300 nm (the specific SiO₂ thickness that optimizes the optical identification depends on the 2D material to be identified).

2. Materials

In Table 1 we present a list of the 2D materials whose apparent color has been reported in the literature. We included the electronic behavior of each material and their bandgap.

Material	Origin	Electronical behavior	# layers	Bandgap (eV)	Reference
Graphite	Natural	Semi-metal	Bulk	0	[11](E)
		Semiconductor	1	0	[12](E)
Graphene oxide	Synthetic	Semiconductor, Insulator	1	0.02-2 (D)	[13](E)
MoS ₂	Natural	Semiconductor	Bulk	1.2 (I)	[14] (E)
			1	1.8 (D)	[15] (E)
WS ₂	Synthetic	Semiconductor	Bulk	1.3 (I)	[14] (E)
			1	2 (D)	
WSe ₂	Synthetic	Semiconductor	Bulk	1.2 (I)	[14] (E)
			1	1.6 (D)	[16] (E)
MoTe ₂	Synthetic	Semiconductor	Bulk	1	[17] (E)
			1	1.1	[18] (T)
1T-TaS ₂	Synthetic	Metallic, Semiconductor	Bulk	0.19	[19](T)
			1	0.39	[19] (T)
2H-TaS ₂	Synthetic	Metallic	Bulk	0	[20] (T)
2H-TaSe ₂	Synthetic	Metallic	Bulk	0	[21] (E)
hBN	Synthetic	Semiconductor	Bulk	5.9 (I)	[22] (E)
γ -InSe	Synthetic	Semiconductor	Bulk	1.2 (I)	[23] (E)
			1	2.4 (D)	
ϵ -GaSe	Synthetic	Semiconductor	Bulk	2.1 (D)	[24](E)
			2	2.4 (I)	[25] (T)
			1	3 (I)	
MoO ₃	Synthetic	Semiconductor	Bulk	3 (D)	[26] (E)
BP	Synthetic	Semiconductor	Bulk	2 (D)	[27,28] (E)
			1	0.3 (D)	
TiS ₃	Synthetic	Semiconductor	Bulk	1 (D)	[29](E)
Bi ₂ Te ₃	Synthetic	Semiconductor	Bulk	0.15 (D)	[30](E)
NiPS ₃	Synthetic	Semiconductor	Bulk	1.7 (I)	[31] (E)
			1	1.8 (I)	[32] (T)

FePS ₃	Synthetic	Semiconductor	bulk	1.59	[31] (E)
MnPS ₃	Synthetic	Semiconductor	bulk	3 (I)	[33] (T)
Franckeite	Natural	Semiconductor	Bulk	0.7 (I)	[34] (E)
CrI ₃	Synthetic	Semiconductor	Bulk	1.2 (D)	[35] (E)
			1	1.1	[36] (T)
PbI ₂	Synthetic	Semiconductor	Bulk	2.41 (I)	[37] (E)
			1	2.47 (D)	
MAPbI ₃	Synthetic	Semiconductor	Bulk	1.5 (D)	[38,39] (E)
(PEA) ₂ PbBr ₄	Synthetic	Semiconductor	Bulk	2.9	[40] (E)
BSSCO	Synthetic	Superconductor	Bulk	0.042	[41] (E)

Table 1. (I) indicates that it is an indirect bandgap, and (D) indicates a direct bandgap.

(E) indicates an experimental value and (T) indicates a theoretical result.

2.1. Graphene

Graphene became the first 2D material isolated, by Novoselov and Geim, in 2004 by mechanical exfoliation^[1]. Its crystal structure is made of carbon atoms, packed in a honeycomb crystal lattice^[42,43], with thickness of about 3 Å^[44]. The carbon atoms are about 1.42 Å from its three neighbors^[45], sharing σ bonds; and the remaining electron per atom is used to make π and π^* bonds between layers when they are stacked. Because of its crystal structure (P6/mmm^[46] space group in international notation), the first Brillouin zone has two inequivalent points K and K' (called Dirac points), where a band crossing occurs^[47]. Due to it, graphene is a zero-gap semiconductor and its charge carriers mimic relativistic particles with zero rest mass, and its energy dispersion has a linear relation near the Dirac points, while they move 300 times less than the speed of light^[12,48]. The peculiarities of the graphene band structure reflect on its electronic properties: It has been measured electronic mobilities up to $2.3 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^2/(\text{V} \cdot \text{s})$ at room temperature^[49], nearly 200 times the mobility of silicon^[50]. Moreover, it possesses withstanding mechanical properties, such as a high Young's Modulus of around 1 TPa and a breaking strength of 130 GPa^[51]. From these properties and others, graphene has proven to be useful in

multiple fields, such as optoelectronics^[52–61], sensors^[62–66], flexible electronics^[67–69], medicine^[70,71], energy storage^[72,73], etc^[74].

Graphene color ranges for different substrate thicknesses showcasing the importance of the flake and the substrate are equivalent for determining the thickness of the flakes. Figure 2(a) shows a collection of optical microscopy images of graphene flakes with thicknesses ranging from single-layer to 15 layers, deposited onto 90 nm SiO₂/Si, with a marked thickness-dependent apparent color. Figure 2(b) depicts the color-bar, with the range that graphene can exhibit from 1L to 125L, paying special attention to the range of 1L-10L deposited on a 100 nm SiO₂/Si. Figure 2(c) shows some flakes ranging from 1L-9L deposited on a 285 nm SiO₂/Si. Figure 2(d) shows a similar collection of images but for flakes deposited onto 300 nm SiO₂/Si substrates where different apparent colors are clearly observed. In each figure one can notice that, from single-layer to multilayer graphene, the samples' reflection for their surface is less intense than that from the SiO₂/Si substrate, resulting in negative value contrasts. The origin of the contrast can be understood thanks to Fresnel's equations, with a physical model like the one depicted in Figure 1, and it is used in several works^[3,4,75].

Figure 2. The number shown on top of each flake corresponds to the amount of monolayers of graphene. (a) Color optical images of 1L-15L graphene flakes on 90 nm SiO₂/Si. The scale bars in each image are 10 μ m. Reprinted with permission from [2]. Copyright (2013) American Chemical Society. (b) Classical numerical color-bar for graphene from 1 to 125 layers. Reprinted from [76]. Copyright (2019), with permission

from Elsevier. (c) Color optical images of 1L-9L of graphene flakes on 285 nm SiO₂/Si, scale bar is not included in the original work. Reprinted with permission from ^[75]. Copyright (2013) American Chemical Society. (d) Color optical images of 1L-13L graphene flakes on 300 nm SiO₂/Si taken at the exposure time of 50 ms. The scale bars are 5 μm. Reprinted with permission from ^[2]. Copyright (2013) American Chemical Society.

These figures can be employed to build up color-charts that correlate the thickness of the graphene flakes with their apparent color. These color-charts will allow other users a fast thickness estimation, but they present the limitation that will be only valid substrates with 90 nm or 300 nm SiO₂. Although the apparent color may appear different due to the specific illumination of each laboratory, properties such as exposure time, white balance, illumination conditions, hue, etc. can be tuned in order to adjust the apparent color to achieve a similar thickness dependent color to the one of the published figures. In fact, as shown in Figure 2, when comparing the (a) panel with the (b) panel, their color-charts seem very different although the difference between the SiO₂ thickness of capping layer substrates is just 10 nm, which is attributed to the different parameters taken on the two publications when the authors acquired the pictures of the samples.

The search of flakes guided by their colors has recently become so common in 2D materials thickness identification that even machine learning algorithms have been developed in order to identify flakes onto SiO₂/Si and PDMS substrates in a faster and more reliable way^[76-79]. The evolution of these new methods gives science new paths to elaborate everyday measurements faster. We think that the standardization of color-charts and the collaborative creation of a color-chart repository is indispensable to follow this trend in the future.

2.2. Graphene oxide

Graphene oxide (GO) is composed of benzene ring regions that are not oxidized and other regions that have aliphatic six-membered rings. The degree of oxidation depends on the relative sizes of these two regions, and they are randomly distributed, meaning that quantifying these values is a complex work. Graphene oxide has different properties when compared to graphene, such as hydrophilicity in GO in contrast to hydrophobicity in graphene^[80], and it is produced easier than its counterpart. The preparation techniques to intercalate oxygen in graphene and synthesize GO are diverse, and they use different reagents and all of their advantages and disadvantages, producing GO with different properties. By tuning the oxidation degree in graphene the bandgap can be manipulated, opening a direct band gap due to the disruption of the π electrons^[81], and it has been changed from 2 to 0.02 eV^[13]. Therefore, it can be used in photodetection for that range of the electromagnetic spectrum. Recently, GO is found to have fluorescent and non-linear optical properties, being possible to use in short pulsed high power lasers^[82]. This material has been functionalized, maintaining the excellent properties and adding new characteristics, typical of the functional groups^[80]. Thus, it has been opened a wide path in diverse applications, not only in electronics, photonics and optoelectronics fields but also, to name some, in biomedical and photocatalytic applications^[83,84]. Due to these features, a non-destructible optical characterization is needed. Figure 3 shows flakes of GO from 1L-5L deposited on top of 300 nm of SiO₂/Si substrate.

Figure 3. GO flake on top of 300 nm of SiO₂/Si substrate from 1L-5L. Below panel shows the apparent color-chart made from these thicknesses. Reprinted from ^[85], Copyright (2013), with permission from Elsevier.

2.3. TMDCs:

Due to the lack of a bandgap in graphene, other materials became more attractive to researchers^[86], and several kinds of materials have been found attending to different properties, creating a 2D library^[87]. Transition Metal Dichalcogenides, usually named after TMDCs, is a family of layered compounds with the typical formula MX₂, where M = Mo, W, Sn, Hf and Zr; and X = S, Se and Te. A monolayer of any of these compounds is composed of three atomic layers following the order X-M-X. They possess no dangling bonds on the basal plane and, as it occurs in graphene, the layers are bonded with van der Waals force, which makes them easy to be exfoliated with different techniques. TMDCs possess diverse electronic properties, and most of them are semiconductors (MoS₂, WS₂ and MoSe₂), although one can also find semimetals (WTe₂ and TiSe₂), insulators (HfS₂)

and even metals (NbS₂ and VSe₂). They have been studied for a long time. In a review in 1969, Wilson J.A. *et al.*^[88] examined these compounds and the well-known structural, optical and electrical properties. Moreover, this family of materials have the property of changing their electronic behavior with thickness. Usually, bulk TMDCs semiconductors possess an indirect bandgap whilst, when they are thinned down to a monolayer, it modifies to a direct one^[16,89].

Moreover, for thick TMDCs (~40-100 nm), strong coupling effect between excitons, typical from these materials, and optical modes in Fabry-Perot microcavities due to light confinement is exhibited. In these systems, Rabi splitting can be observed whether placing the TMDC between two metallic mirrors or just onto a well reflecting substrate, e.g. SiO₂/Si^[90,91]. These strong coupling between cavity modes and excitons may lead to substantial changes in apparent colors of these materials.

Nowadays, the family of TMDCs is very attractive in applications such as photonics, electronics, optoelectronics^[92], sensors^[93,94], and so on^[95,96].

2.3.1. MoS₂:

Among the TMDCs, MoS₂ has been the most studied material. It has been identified as 2D after the discovery of graphene. MoS₂ is formed by stacking layers, bonded with van der Waals forces, and it possesses three polytypes. In this work, we are going to focus on the 2H one (hexagonal polymorph), with an in-plane hexagonal *P6₃/mmc* crystal structure, in which the molybdenum atoms are in the centers of trigonal prisms formed by the sulfur^[97]. MoS₂ is already well-known for its applications in the fields of lubrication^[98], catalysis^[99] and petroleum desulfuration^[100] for long time; but in the last years, its optical, electronic and optoelectronic properties have also started to be

intriguing to the scientific community. When the MoS₂ is exfoliated to one layer (of thickness around 0.7 nm^[101]), its energy bandgap changes from indirect, with a value of ~1.2 eV at its Γ point, to a direct bandgap of 1.8 eV at its K point^[14,89,102]. Moreover, it has been proven that this bandgap can be tuned by applying strain, as it happens with various TMDCs^[103–105]. Thus, the electronic properties of monolayer MoS₂ make it a suitable candidate for applications in transistors, achieving higher on/off ratio than that of graphene, and in optoelectronic devices^[106].

Figure 4 shows the calculated C of MoS₂ from 1L to 8L by using substrates of 100 nm SiO₂ (Figure 4(a)) and 300 nm SiO₂ (Figure 4(b)). Here, it is well depicted how the maximum and minimum values of the function move along the wavelength for MoS₂ flakes with different thicknesses on the same substrate.

Figure 4. Plots of calculated C for 1L-8L MoS₂ on (a) 100 nm SiO₂ and (b) 300 nm SiO₂ as a function of wavelength. Adapted from^[76]. Copyright (2019), with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 5 shows optical microscopy images of few-layer MoS₂ flakes of different thickness deposited onto 90 nm (Figure 5(a)) and 300 nm SiO₂/Si (Figure 5(b)). The panels (b) and (c) come from two different works, showing a change of apparent color due to the

different parameters that the authors have used in their experiments. As we have already seen, these flakes show a marked thickness-dependent apparent color that depends on the specific SiO₂ thickness used. In addition, these figures can be employed to build up color-charts that correlate the thickness of MoS₂ flakes with their apparent color on SiO₂/Si substrates with 90 nm and 300 nm SiO₂ capping layer.

Figure 5. Numbers in each flake indicate the amount of MoS₂ monolayers in each case.

(a) Color optical images of 1L-15L MoS₂ flakes on 90 nm SiO₂/Si substrate. The scale bar is 5 μ m for each image. Reprinted with permission from [2]. Copyright (2013) American Chemical Society. (b) Color optical images of 1L-15L MoS₂ on 300 nm SiO₂/Si

substrate. The scale bars are 5 μm for images from 1L-11L and 10 μm for the image of 12L. Reprinted with permission from [2]. Copyright (2013) American Chemical Society.

(c) Color-charts of MoS_2 from 1-125 layers on 300 nm SiO_2/Si substrate. Reprinted from [76]., Copyright (2019), with permission from Elsevier.

Chemical vapor deposition (CVD) method is the most common technique to grow monolayer MoS_2 on different substrates, and it is well developed and reproducible. Figure 6 shows MoS_2 monolayer flakes grown by CVD using sapphire (panel (a)) and 280 nm SiO_2/Si (panel (b)) as substrates as well as monolayer MoS_2 on quartz substrate (panel (c)) by using mechanical exfoliation method.

Figure 6. MoS_2 monolayer flakes grown by CVD technique on (a) sapphire. Adapted from [107]. And (b) 280 nm SiO_2/Si . Scale bar corresponds to 10 μm . Adapted from [108]. (c) Mechanically exfoliated MoS_2 monolayer deposited on quartz. Scale bar corresponds to 5 μm . Adapted from [109]. Copyright (2016), with permission from John Wiley and Sons.

2.3.2. WS_2 :

Tungsten disulfide (WS_2) is another material that becomes very interesting to scientific community due to many intriguing assets, such as high spin-orbit coupling, high emission quantum yield [110], and large exciton and trion binding energy [111–113]. Hexagonal polymorph type (2H) structure, the most stable one with a monolayer thickness of ~ 0.6

nm^[114], has an indirect bandgap of ~1.3 eV in bulk. When it is thinned down to a monolayer, a direct bandgap of ~2 eV is obtained ^[14,16,115], similar to that of MoS₂. This change in bandgap is useful in renewable energy conversion and storage fields, such as electrocatalysis, photocatalysis, batteries and supercapacitors^[116]. Moreover, monolayer WS₂ has become as a promising material for fields like valleytronics, photonic and photoluminescence enhancement^[117]. But it also features intriguing properties when it is studied in few-layers, paving a way in electronics, optoelectronics, photovoltaics and thermoelectricity applications^[118–120].

Figure 7 shows WS₂ flakes deposited onto three different Si substrates with SiO₂ capping layer of 88, 215 and 297 nm, respectively, building the apparent color charts to identify thin films of WS₂ on these substrates.

Figure 7. WS₂ flakes and corresponding color-charts onto Si substrates with (a) 88, (b) 215 and (c) 297 nm SiO₂ capping layers from top to bottom, respectively.

Figure 8 exhibits WS₂ flakes deposited onto 300 nm SiO₂/Si substrate, displaying the apparent color of 1L-4L WS₂ on this substrate.

Figure 8. The optical image and color-charts of 1L-4L WS₂ flakes deposited onto 300 nm SiO₂/Si substrate. Reprinted from ^[121]. Copyright (2017), with permission from John Wiley and Sons.

2.3.3. WSe₂:

Tungsten diselenide in its 2H polytype^[122], is another renowned member of the TMDCs family, which also experiments a transition from indirect (~ 1.2 eV in bulk^[14]) to direct (~ 1.6 eV^[16]) bandgap and an increase on the photoluminescence intensity when it is studied as monolayer, with a thickness of ~ 0.63 nm^[123]. In this material spin orbit coupling (SOC) is more enhanced in comparison to other TMDCs^[124], making it as a promising candidate for spintronic applications. WSe₂ is useful in similar applications as is WS₂, which are electrocatalysis, batteries, photocatalysis, solar energy conversion, etc.^[125]. Moreover, bulk and mechanically exfoliated monolayer or thin film WSe₂ flakes present a p-type electrical conduction, which makes it very interesting for electronic applications^[123,126] and high carrier mobility transistors using WSe₂ monolayer flakes^[127].

Thus, characterization of few-layer tungsten diselenide is mandatory for its use in these applications.

Figure 9 shows two collections of optical microscopy (OM) images and corresponding color-charts of few-layer WSe₂ flakes with different thickness deposited onto 90 nm (Figure 9(a)) and 300 nm (Figure 9(c)) SiO₂/Si substrates, respectively. Below the flakes' OM pictures, one can find their respective color-charts, correlating the thickness of WSe₂ flakes with their apparent color when they are placed onto 90 nm and 300 nm SiO₂/Si substrates. Figure 9(c) shows the color-charts of few-layer WSe₂ flakes on 287 nm SiO₂/Si substrate with thickness ranging from 1L to 50 nm.

Figure 9. The numbers indicate the amount of layers of WSe₂ flakes. Color optical images of 1L-14L WSe₂ flakes on (a) 90 nm and (c) 300 nm SiO₂/Si substrates. The scale bars shown in (a) and (c) have a length of 5 μm and 2 μm , respectively. Reprinted with permission from ^[2]. Copyright (2013) American Chemical Society. (b) Color-chart built from WSe₂ flakes on 287 nm SiO₂/Si substrate. Reprinted from ^[128] with the permission of AIP publishing.

2.3.4. MoTe₂:

Molybdenum ditelluride crystal structure is organized in a honeycomb lattice and it has an indirect bandgap of 0.93 eV when it is measured in bulk, raising to a direct one of 1.08 eV when it is monolayer, with stronger photoluminescence^[129]. Similar to GaSe and InSe, it has been found that MoTe₂ samples are not stable in air. Chen, B. et al.^[130] have noticed that monolayers, around 0.7 nm thick, of MoTe₂ flakes are stable for up to eight days in ambient exposure, but their optical properties are largely affected, i.e. optical contrast and PL intensity. This aging process is related to the binding of O₂ molecules to Mo and Te atoms, absorbed at defect sites. Besides, other studies using theoretical investigations have suggested that adsorption of nonmetal atoms on the surface of MoTe₂ may create a magnetic moment locally, and MoTe₂ monolayers might show long-range antiferromagnetic ordering due to adsorption of H atoms onto it^[131].

The apparent colors of 1L, 4L and 5L MoTe₂ deposited on 300 nm SiO₂/Si substrate are extracted from the picture shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Optical microscopy image and color-charts of few-layer MoTe₂ flakes deposited onto 300 nm SiO₂/Si substrate. Reprinted from ^[121]. Copyright (2017), with permission from John Wiley and Sons.

2.4. TaS₂:

TaS₂ presents two typical crystal polytype structures: octahedral (1T) and hexagonal (2H) with complex electronic behaviors, showing dependence on the temperature and the number of layers. Recently, 2D charge density wave materials, such as 1T-TaS₂^[132–134] and 2H-TaS₂^[135], among other TMDCs, have attracted interest as high performance functional materials^[136]. A charge density wave is a ground state led by the interaction of electrons and phonons and it is associated with a periodic distortion of the crystal lattice in one dimension^[137].

The 1T polytype shows a metal-insulator transition at a temperature of 350 K, and another one at 190 K involving two semiconducting phases^[138]. Although 1T-TaS₂ is not superconductor, it shows superconductivity when a pressure of dozens of GPa is applied^[134], this behavior depends on the temperature^[139–141]. Besides, 1T-TaS₂ has been developed as a catalyst when it is placed on a nanoporous gold substrate, achieving high hydrogen evolution reaction performance^[142,143], reaching values comparable to that of commercial Pt-C catalyst. This compound can be synthesized in quantum dots (QDs), changing its properties when the grain size of 1T-TaS₂ QDs is reduced. It features a monolayer thickness of ~0.8 nm^[144]. It exhibits an increase of the bandgap from indirect to direct due to confinement effect in the electronic structure^[145].

Figure 11 shows a collection of optical microscopy images of few-layer 1T-TaS₂ flakes of different thickness deposited onto 90 nm SiO₂/Si substrate. The bottom panel of Figure 11 shows the color-charts correlating the thickness of 1T-TaS₂ flakes with their apparent color.

Figure 11. Color optical images of 1L-28L and 32L 1T-TaS₂ flakes on 90 nm SiO₂/Si. The scale bars are 5 μm. The numbers indicate the number of 1T-TaS₂ layers. The bottom panel shows the corresponding color-charts of 1T-TaS₂ flakes. Reprinted with permission from ^[2]. Copyright (2013) American Chemical Society.

Figure 12 shows a two optical microscopy images of thin film 1T-TaS₂ flakes deposited onto 285 nm SiO₂/Si substrate. Along with it, AFM measurements are included to provide a coarse value of the thickness of the 1T-TaS₂ flakes.

Figure 12. (a), (d) Color optical images of thin films 1T-TaS₂ flakes on 285 nm SiO₂/Si. (b), (c), (e) and (f) images correspond to AFM measurements of the flakes. The scale bars are 10 μm. Adapted from ^[19].

The 2H polytype shows charge density waves (at a critical temperature of 75 K^[146]) and superconductivity transitions (below 1.75 K^[147]), with a metallic electronic behavior at low temperatures^[20,148]. It has been observed that superconductivity persists when the material is thinned down to 3.5 nm thickness, the equivalent to 5 covalent planes^[132], being the thickness of a monolayer ~ 0.6 nm^[149]. It has been observed that this polytype possesses chiral charge density waves, which coexists with superconductivity^[147]. Moreover, the superconducting state can be tuned, rising its transition temperature when Na atoms or pyridine molecules are intercalated in 2H-TaS₂^[150,151]. This polytype has also found its place on the solar cell field, obtaining high efficiencies when thin films are used as an electron transport layer in perovskite-based devices^[152].

In Figure 13 it is shown the color-chart of a single-layer 2H-TaS₂ flake onto a 285 nm SiO₂/Si substrate, along with its AFM image and thickness statistics, showing a thickness

Figure 13. Optical microscopy image of an atomically thin 2H-TaS₂ flake deposited onto a 285 nm SiO₂/Si substrate, along with the respective color-chart of the monolayer flakes in the dashed square. Adapted from ^[132].

2.5. TaSe₂:

2H-TaSe₂ is a layered polytype, having an hexagonal crystal symmetry with metallic behavior at room temperature ^[21], however it shows up to three orders of magnitude to values for classical metals. When the material is in bulk, it has proved to have phase transitions at certain temperatures: from metallic to incommensurate charge density wave, at 123 K, and to commensurate charge-density wave at 90 K ^[21].

Recently, Raman measurements at low temperature have exhibited the existence of incommensurate charge density waves phase transition in thin layers (less than 5 layers) of 2H-TaSe₂. This material in thin film has been currently used in the fabrication of FETs and it has proved to have potential for optoelectronic applications^[153].

Figure 14 depicts the apparent color for 2L-5L 2H-TaSe₂ flakes deposited onto 300 nm SiO₂/Si substrate and the corresponding color-charts.

Figure 14. Color optical image of 2L-5L 2H-TaSe₂ flakes on 300 nm SiO₂/Si. The scale bar is 10 μm. The bottom panel shows the corresponding color-charts of 2H-TaSe₂ flakes. Adapted from ^[154].

2.6. hBN:

Hexagonal boron nitride (hBN) is a very stable, highly anisotropic crystal with strong covalent bonds between boron and nitrogen in the in-plane direction and vdW bonds between layers^[155–157]. It exhibits an indirect wide bandgap of ~ 4-7 eV^[156–161], which is independent on the thickness of hBN when it is varied from bulk to monolayer. For several decades, hBN has been used as a thermally stable ceramic^[162]. Latterly, it has also been employed as substrate, due to its atomically smooth surface with almost free of dangling bonds^[163]. This property is commonly used to encapsulate graphene, TMDCs and other 2D materials, considering that it protects them from degradation and enhances electronic transport^{[163–167][166,167]}. Besides, it is used to enhance the photoluminescence of TMDCs (i.e. MoS₂) in micro-cavities^[168].

hBN is known to be a hyperbolic material, meaning that it has different values of refractive index along different directions and also the permittivity is opposite in sign^[162]. Related to this property of hBN, phonon polaritons propagation has been observed^[169], using it for a broad variety of potential applications^[170-174]. Moreover, hBN thin film is a very promising candidate for quantum photonics working along 2D vdW materials^[175-180] but also nonlinear optical properties have been observed in this material^[181,182].

Figure 15(a) shows an AFM measurement of hBN flake deposited onto SiO₂/Si substrate. Figure 15(b-f) show a collection of optical microscopy images of the same few-layer hBN flake deposited onto 50, 88, 148, 215, 271 and 297 nm SiO₂/Si, respectively. Figure 15(g) exhibits the corresponding color-charts, built up to correlate the thickness of hBN flake with their apparent color on the multiple SiO₂/Si substrates.

Figure 15. (a) AFM image of hBN flake with thickness ranging from 9 nm to 102 nm. (b)-(f) The corresponding optical images of the hBN flake placed onto 50, 88, 148, 215, 271 and 297 nm SiO₂/Si substrates, respectively. (g) AFM thickness bar and color-bars of hBN flakes deposited on 50-297 nm SiO₂/Si substrates.

2.7. Group III-VI compounds:

The group III-VI family, with the typical formula M^{III}X^{VI} (M = Ga, In; X = S, Se, Te), is found very interesting because of their intriguing optoelectronic and electronic properties. Besides, M^{III}X^{VI} family has been used in flexible devices and, in contrast to TMDCs, they

exhibit thickness-independent direct bandgap, second harmonic generation (SHG), and p-type electronic behavior (infrequent property in TMDCs), among other assets. In addition, it has been observed that strain can be used in these materials to modify their properties^[183,184]. Because of these and more features, $M^{III}X^{VI}$ group forms promising candidates to be used in optics, electronics and optoelectronics applications^[185].

2.7.1. InSe:

Exfoliation of few-layer indium selenide (InSe) has been achieved recently by Mudd, et al.^[186], who discovered the thickness-dependent bandgap of the material (from 1.2 eV for 10 layers to 2.4 eV for monolayer^[23], with 0.8 nm of thickness^[187]). This striking discovery is explained by the interlayer coupling effect, which has impact on other properties in thin films^[23]. Indium selenide can adopt various complex stoichiometries and several phases^[188]. Specifically γ -rhombohedral InSe (which unit cell is made of four layers of monoatomic sheets in the way: Se-In-In-Se^[188]) is a direct bandgap semiconductor which owns anisotropic electronic properties and a high carrier mobility. When its thickness is thinned down, the direct bandgap changes to an indirect one, opposite in behavior compared to MoS_2 ^[189]. The scientific community has focused on the fabrication of InSe-based optoelectronic devices, due to its easiness of use and the good features, showing very high responsivities in photodetectors^[185,190–198]. This material has proven to possess superior responsivities and fast responses when it is used in photodetector^[185]. Furthermore, it can be combined with other 2D materials, forming heterostructures. Zhao Q., et al. have enhanced I-V behavior by building Schottky diodes based on Au/graphite/InSe heterostructures^[199], when compared to Au/InSe heterostructures. Also, photoresponsivity performance and external quantum efficiency can also be improved by introducing graphene flakes^[200].

Overall, InSe flakes are advantageous to work with electronic and optoelectronic applications. Figure 16 shows a color-chart of InSe deposited onto a 271 nm SiO₂/Si substrate.

Figure 16. The top panel shows InSe flakes ranging from 4 nm to 90 nm placed onto a 271 nm SiO₂/Si substrate. The bottom panel shows the corresponding color-chart of InSe flakes. Adapted from [3].

2.7.2. GaSe:

Gallium selenide is another compound that belongs to the M^{III}X^{VI} group. The monolayer, with a value of 0.8 nm of thickness^[201,202], consists of four atomic layers as Se-Ga-Ga-Se. Several modifications in the stacking sequence can lead different space groups, being the most important polytypes β-GaSe, ε-GaSe and γ-GaSe^[203]. The ε-GaSe polytype is the main stacking order when it is found in bulk^[204]. It has an indirect bandgap of 2.1 eV, and another direct bandgap of only 25 meV higher^[24]. Furthermore, the bandgap gets larger to 3 eV when its thickness decreases to monolayer^{[205][25]}, which is useful in optoelectronics^[205]. As its counterpart InSe, GaSe has been constantly employed in photodetectors, achieving outstanding values of photoresponses times, which are comparable, and even faster, to those devices made with other currently used materials^[57,206–209]. Besides, GaSe owns nonlinear optical properties as a result of an absence of the inversion symmetry center. A work carried out by Karvonen et al. found

nonlinear optical features of SHG and third harmonic generation in thin films of GaSe^[210]. Moreover, SHGs in InSe and GaSe are produced in odd and even number of layers^[187], in comparison to 2D TMDCs and hBN, in which this property has a dependence on the number of layers^[121]. One of the drawbacks of GaSe is its environmental degradation, which can be easily overcome by encapsulating it with hBN^[211].

Figure 17 shows a color-chart of GaSe flakes with thicknesses ranging from 8 to 41 nm deposited onto a 271 nm SiO₂/Si substrate

Figure 17: Top panel shows the optical images of GaSe flakes with thicknesses ranging from 8 nm to 41 nm placed onto a 271 nm SiO₂/Si substrate. The bottom panel shows the corresponding color-chart of GaSe flakes. Reprinted from ^[212] with permission from Elsevier .

2.8. Metal Oxides

Metal oxides (MO) are very abundant in Earth's crust, and they are known for centuries to the humanity. They have different electronic structures, charge transport mechanisms or defect states, to name some, when compared to silicon and III-V compounds. Wide bandgap metal oxides have been widely used as transparent conductive oxides (TCO) electrodes in p-n junctions or photovoltaics. MO can be used as collectors of electrons or

holes, depending on the semiconductor/electrode arrangement. If the transparent electrode collects holes and the metal electrode electrons, it is named as conventional architecture. If the MO collect electrons, it is named as inverted architecture^[213].

2.8.1. MoO_3 :

Molybdenum trioxide (MoO_3) is a metal oxide which has different phases with different crystal structures. In its α phase it is a vdW material, with a single-layer thickness of 0.7 nm^[214], and a direct bandgap of nearly 3 eV^[26,215,216]. It is widely used in optical applications such as anode buffer layer in organic photovoltaics^[217], commonly used as a hole selective layer^[218], enhancing the open-circuit voltage and fill factor parameters. It has also been used in perovskite solar cells^[14] and in silicon heterojunction solar cells^[219]. By adding MoO_3 layers from 3 to 20 nm as buffer layer in organic light-emitting diodes, it has improved the efficiency, the stability and the lifetime, reaching the 5000 h of use^[220,221]. Its α phase consists in an orthorhombic structure, which is formed by a double-layer stacking of linked MoO_6 octahedra in the b direction, along which the layers are bounded by vdW forces. Its crystal structure possesses an in-plane anisotropy with different unit cell parameters^[222–226]. Recently, we have studied its mechanical and optical anisotropy in thin films, using a new optical method to identify the orientation of the material based on the change of refractive index, and finding one of the largest in-plane anisotropic Young's modulus so far^[227]. Anisotropic optical materials show diverse and complex optical properties^[174,228,229]. α - MoO_3 exhibits a highly anisotropic propagation of phonon polaritons^[230–233], which can be used to reduce optical losses and improve light confinements^[234–237]. Recently, a theoretical study has shown that the bandgap of MoO_3 can be modified by distorting its crystal lattice, and these variations are different when

the strain is applied along the three axes^[238]. Figures 18(a-d) show several flakes of MoO₃ deposited onto 88, 148, 271 and 297 nm SiO₂/Si substrates, respectively.

Figure 18. The optical microscopy images of MoO₃ flakes placed onto (a) 88, (b) 148, (c) 271 and (d) 297 nm SiO₂/Si substrates. The MoO₃ flakes have thicknesses ranging from (a)14-88 nm, (b) 9-95 nm, (c) 10-100 nm and (d) 5-93 nm. The bottom panel in each line shows the corresponding color-chart of MoO₃ flakes. Adapted from ^[4].

2.9. BP

Phosphorus has several allotropes and the most stable one is called black phosphorous (BP), which is a layered material with strong in-plane anisotropy, each layer forming a

puckered surface due to sp^3 hybridization. It has a layer-tunable direct energy bandgap that varies from 2 eV for monolayer, which has been predicted theoretically and measured experimentally^[28,239], and a value of 0.3 eV in bulk^[27], as it happens to III-VI compounds, changing monotonically with the addition of layers. This property makes BP a promising candidate in applications such as optoelectronic in the wavelength range from ~ 0.6 - 1.5 μm . Its use in photodetectors has yielded high external quantum efficiencies (EQE) and avalanche gain^[240]. This kind of photodetectors has been carried out using other 2D materials and they show higher responsivity values, although most of them cannot be used in the IR range of the spectrum and BP-based photodetectors show faster response time^[161,205,241]. Photodetectors using few-layer BP flakes have achieved broadband detection and fast response^[242]. This difference may be due to the origin of the photoresponse in BP phototransistors, showing that it is dominated by thermally driven thermoelectric and bolometric processes, not photovoltaic effect as usual^[243,244]. In photothermoelectric devices, a difference in temperature is built in the detector, driving the charge carriers from the hot end to the cold end, thus setting an electrical field on the device (process known as Seebeck effect). Therefore, an ideal photothermoelectric detector should have a big light absorption coefficient and a small heat capacity. Besides, a large Seebeck coefficient and a small resistance are required to achieve high responsivity^[245].

A high drawback of BP is its chemical instability when it is exposed to ambient conditions. It has been observed an increase of 200% in volume of few-layer BP flakes due to the condensation of water molecules in the surroundings^[246]. Usually, an encapsulation process is used to protect this material from degradation, while it has been found that chemical doping also improves the stability^[247].

As shown in the top panel of Figure 19, it depicts BP flakes of thicknesses ranging from 4 nm to 98 nm placed on 88 nm SiO₂/Si substrate using deterministic transfer methods. As shown in the bottom panel, the BP flakes are deposited on 297 nm SiO₂/Si substrate, with thicknesses ranging from 9 nm to 94 nm. Color-charts are extracted from BP flakes with thickness ranging from 4 nm and 9 nm, respectively, up to 100 nm.

Figure 19. Optical microscopy (OM) images of BP flakes onto 88 (top) and 297 (bottom) nm SiO₂/Si substrates. Bottom panels of OM images are the corresponding color-charts of BP flakes with thickness ranging from 4 nm (for 88 nm SiO₂/Si) and 9 nm (for 297 nm SiO₂/Si) to 100 nm.

Figure 20 shows other BP flakes deposited on 300 nm SiO₂/Si substrate, including the color-bar up to 80 nm, and paying special attention to the first 10 layers. The difference between the apparent color of SiO₂ shown in Figure 19 and Figure 20 is due to the different parameters in both works when taking the pictures, as we have already discussed.

Figure 20. Optical image and corresponding color-chart of BP flakes onto 300 nm SiO₂/Si. Bottom panel shows the specific identification of the first 10 layers. Reprinted from ^[248]. Copyright (2016), with permission from John Wiley and Sons.

2.10. TiS₃

Transition metal trichalcogenides (TMTCs), with the formula MX₃ (where M = Ti, Zr, Hf, etc. and X = S, Se, Te), is another 2D family with members that present many different electronic properties. This group of materials possess a wide range of bandgap values, making them suitable for applications including field-effect transistors, a broad range of photodetectors, and others attending their anisotropic properties^[249,250]. TMTCs are also layered materials, with layers bonded by vdW forces^[251]. TiS₃ is a well-known material from this family, and its atoms in single-layer are arranged in a crystal structure of trigonal prism showing in-plane anisotropic properties, such as linear dichroism and different mobility values^[252,253]. TiS₃ is characterized to have an optical bandgap of 1 eV^[29] in bulk (and another energy gap of 1.4 eV appears when this material is presented in thin films or powders^[254]). Recently, it has started to be interesting to the scientific community due

to its attractive properties such as low-cost production, abundant and nontoxic elements, and the easiness of the process of synthesis^[251,255]. TiS₃ has been also studied as a thermoelectric material^[256] which thermal conductivity can be enhanced by adding impurities atoms^[257]. The aforementioned properties can be tuned by inducing an external strain^[258] in few-layers of TiS₃, finding a change in the bandgap from direct to indirect when the strain is applied along a certain axis. Moreover, electrical and photoelectronic devices have been built with this material^[259] featuring a high mobility. These properties, combined with the direct bandgap and its in-plane anisotropy, are enough to prove that TiS₃ is a good candidate for photodetectors^[260].

Therefore, characterizing the thickness of this material prior to the applications mentioned before is critical for the advances in this field. Figure 21 depicts TiS₃ nanoribbons with thickness ranging from 5 nm to 110 nm and its color-chart on 90 nm SiO₂/Si substrate.

Figure 21. Optical images and a color-chart of TiS₃ flakes with thickness up to 110 nm onto 90 nm SiO₂/Si substrate. The scale bars are 5 μm. Adapted from ^[261].

2.11. Bi₂Te₃

Bismuth telluride (Bi₂Te₃) is a layered material with a rhombohedral lattice^[262,263], and a semiconductor crystal with a direct bandgap of 0.15 eV^[30]. It is a well-known thermoelectric material that has been widely used for decades and thoroughly developed to enhance its thermoelectric properties, such as reducing its dimension and shapes^[264]. Currently, the investigations in thermoelectric materials are focused on the high-temperature region, although Bi₂Te₃ works in the low-temperature region of 200-500 K, usually in micro-environmental cooling and Peltier effect^[265]. Bi₂Te₃ is synthesized with several techniques, but the most suitable one is the solvothermal process. Depending on the process used, the product material can vary from nanoparticles to single crystals with a wide range of thicknesses from a few nm to hundreds of them^[266–268]. Thus, a characterization presented in Figure 22 is needed in order to accurately determine the thickness of this material with optical method.

Figure 22. Theoretical color-charts of Bi₂Te₃ with thickness of 1-10 nm (i.e., 1–10 L) on (a) 457 nm SiO₂/Si and (b) 180 μm mica substrates. Reproduced with permission from^[269]. © IOP Publishing. All rights reserved.

2.12. Metal phosphochalcogenides

Another family of layered materials have emerged, phosphochalcogenides, with the typical formula of MPX₃ (M = Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, etc. and X = S, Se). These materials tend

to crystallize in a monoclinic structure, shaping a honeycomb lattice^[270–272], and having a small cleavage energy between planes^[273], thus indicating they can be easily exfoliated. This class of chalcogenides is used in catalytic and optoelectronic applications, with a wide bandgap ranging from 1.3 to 3.5 eV. A family of MPX_3 can be intercalated with alkali ions in its van der Waals gap and pave a way for batteries applications, being used as cathode and anode materials^[274]. Using monolayers of phosphochalcogenides in lithium-ion batteries, stability and specific capacity are enhanced when compared to other layered materials^[275]. Nowadays, it is being studied the possible use of these materials as cathodes in batteries of future NASA's missions to Venus^[274].

2.12.1. $NiPS_3$

Among the MPX_3 compounds, $NiPS_3$ is an important element in this family of materials. It has proven to possess antiferromagnetic properties and have an experimental indirect energy bandgap of 1.7 eV^[31]. Interestingly, when the material is thinned down, its monoclinic crystal structure changes to the hexagonal D_{3d} in a monolayer, and the change of the lattice constant of the material yields a change in the energy bandgap to 1.8 eV^[32]. The antiferromagnetic behavior also changes when the material becomes single layer and the zigzag and Néels orders are virtually degenerated, thus facilitating large magnetic fluctuations. Recently, it has been reported the first fabrication of field effect transistor with $NiPS_3$, revealing an n-type semiconductor. By using few-layers oriented crystals of $NiPS_3$, it has been obtained On/Off ratios of orders of magnitude similar to the ones found in graphene^[276]. Besides, the mobility variation with thickness is comparable to the devices using TMDCs. Chu J. et al.^[277] have built UV photodetectors with few-layers of $NiPS_3$, using the shift of typical Raman peaks to quickly identify the thickness of the

samples used. The ultrathin NiPS₃ flakes exhibit comparable photoresponse to other 2D materials-based devices, i.e., MoS₂, MoSe₂, graphene and graphene oxide.

As shown in Figure 23, the apparent color of 1-4L and 7L of NiPS₃ is extracted when it is deposited on a 90 nm SiO₂/Si substrate.

Figure 23. Optical image and corresponding color-chart of NiPS₃ flakes with thickness ranging from 1L to 4 L as well as 7L onto 90 nm of SiO₂/Si. Adapted from [278].

2.12.2. FePS₃:

FePS₃ is a magnetic semiconductor with an energy gap of 1.59 eV [31] and intrinsic antiferromagnetic when the temperature is below its Néel temperature (120 K).

Its structural properties change with dimensionality, when this material is studied in its bulk form, it has a monoclinic structure, with the point group C_{2h} [279], whereas it is found in monolayer, it belongs to the D_{3d} factor group [280]. When the material is thinned down, the positions of Raman peaks P4 and P5 move away, which can be useful to determine the thickness of the sample [270]. The distribution of the magnetic carriers is described as parallel ferromagnetic chains antiferromagnetically coupled between them in a plane [281]. Intriguingly, this antiferromagnetic distribution is conserved even to the monolayer

thickness ^[270]. Its intrinsic magnetism makes this material a suitable one for magneto-optics and 2D spintronics applications.

In Figure 24 it is shown a FePS₃ flake with thicknesses from 8-32 nm, deposited onto a substrate of 272 nm of SiO₂ thickness of capping layer.

Figure 24: Optical image and corresponding color-chart of FePS₃ flakes with thickness ranging from 8 nm to 32 nm onto 272 nm of SiO₂/Si. Adapted from ^[282].

2.12.3. MnPS₃:

MnPS₃ shares the same crystal structure of the other phosphochalcogenides discussed before and a magnetic behavior similar to them, with an indirect bandgap of ~3eV ^[33]. MnPS₃ shows an antiferromagnetic behavior, showing the same magnetic ordering performance down not just to bilayer MnPS₃ flakes ^[283], but even to the monolayer limit ^[284], paving a way in the of 2D antiferromagnet materials field. Its Néel temperature decreases slightly from 78 K, when it is studied in bulk, to 66 K when it is thinned down to three layers ^[285]; implying that the van der Waals interaction between the layers stabilizes the magnetic order. Besides, a broadening of its P₂ Raman mode occurs when the material is close to the Néel temperature. It is worth to highlight the fields where it can be useful, such as electrocatalysis ^[286], photocatalysis ^[287], electron tunnelling ^[288], valleytronics ^[289] and devices applications ^[290].

Figure 25 shows a MnPS₃ flake with 1, 2 and 4 layers thick, deposited onto 90 nm SiO₂/Si

substrate.

Figure 25: Optical image and corresponding color-chart of MnPS₃ flakes with 1, 2 and 4 layers placed onto 90 nm of SiO₂/Si. Adapted from ^[291].

2.13. Franckeite:

Fabrication of van der Waals heterostructures is a way to build devices with outstanding optical, optoelectronic and electrical properties, among others. Nonetheless, the correct delamination/deposition of the materials and the following fabrication of these devices are large engineering challenge that must be overcome. These problems have led to find other naturally occurring van der Waals heterostructures as materials for such devices, such as Franckeite. Franckeite is a layered material, and its crystal structure is a complex composition of stacks of pseudo-hexagonal (H) and pseudo-tetragonal (Q) layers. The H layers are formed by four atomic layers of sulfide compounds with molecular formula of MS, being M = Pb²⁺, Sn²⁺ or Sb³⁺. And the Q layers are formed by a MS₂ formula, where

$M = \text{Sn}^{4+}$ or Fe^{2+} [34]. The alternation of these slabs gives the material anisotropic properties although the material itself is made by alternating isotropic layers [292]. This superlattice system exhibits interestingly a transversal modulation along the b direction and a non-modulation in the a direction [293]. Where the c direction is perpendicular to the plane (a - b), in which the layers are bonded with van der Waals forces.

Frisenda et al. [294] have recently studied the rippling that this material exhibits an inhomogeneous in-plane strain profile and anisotropic vibrational properties, using linearly polarized light with Raman spectroscopy measurements. They have investigated also anisotropic electrical and optical properties, showing linear dichroism. Due to this odd structure, franckeite has an experimental monolayer thickness of 2.4-3.5 nm measured with an AFM, which is in agreement with the single unit cell of ~1.8 nm using cross-section TEM measurements [295].

Franckeite has been thoroughly examined by several groups, finding an experimental electronic indirect bandgap of 0.7 eV in bulk [34]. Electronic and structural properties changes have not been correlated to the number of sheets, as it happens in other materials, although it exhibits a change in the intensity of Raman peaks with the thickness [295]. The lack of change is explained by the large thickness of a monolayer in this material and thus the weak interactions that franckeite layers feel to each other. Moreover, franckeite exhibits a superior stability after exfoliation in ambient conditions (up to 6 months) [295], although the degradation becomes very fast when it is thinned down to a monolayer. Its small bandgap and high stability make this material a candidate to replace black phosphorus in optoelectronic applications and solar cells, showing a fast response with light [296]. Furthermore, this material can be used in other applications, such as surface plasmon resonance sensors, biological analysis, environmental monitoring, food safety or chemical sensors [297-300].

Figure 26 shows the apparent colors of franckeite flakes on 292 nm (Figure 26b) and 92 nm (Figure 26e) SiO₂/Si substrates.

Figure 26. OM images of franckeite flakes (a) on a Gel-film carrier substrate with Transmission mode. (b) Onto a 292 nm SiO₂/Si substrate, after transfer, with epillumination OM and (c) atomic force microscopy images. The color chart below (a)-(c) serves as a guide to determine the thickness of franckeite flakes on 292 nm SiO₂/Si substrates. (d-f) Same images as shown in (a)-(c) but for a franckeite flake transferred onto a 92 nm SiO₂/Si substrate. The color chart below (d) to (f) serves as a guide to determine the thickness of franckeite flakes on 92 nm SiO₂/Si substrates. Reproduced from [301].

2.14. CrI₃

Chromium iodide belongs to the family of Chromium trihalides CrX_3 ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}$), which are magnetic layered materials^[302]. CrI_3 has a phase transition from the monoclinic to the rhombohedral type upon cooling from room temperature^[303]. CrI_3 has a direct band gap of ~ 1.2 eV^[35], lowering to a theoretical indirect band gap of 1.1 eV^[36] when it is thinned down to monolayer. From the CrX_3 family, it possesses the highest ferromagnetic Curie temperature, so far^[35], with a value of $T_c = 68$ K. The stacking-dependent effect of the magnetization is strong, changing from antiferromagnetic when studied as bilayer^[304], and ferromagnetic when is presented as monolayer, besides lowering its T_c down to 45 K^[305]. This ferromagnetic behavior in monolayer samples can transition to antiferromagnetic when a compressive strain is applied^[306,307]. For a bilayer system, if a tensile strain is applied, the antiferromagnetic phase stabilizes, while a compressive strain transform the system ferromagnetic; besides, a change in the T_c is observed when a strain is induced^[308]. The magnetism exhibited in a bilayer system can be controlled with electrical currents by tuning the gate voltage, showing magnetoelectric effects^[309]. These aforementioned properties make this material suitable for spintronic and optoelectronic applications.

Figure 27 shows the characteristic apparent color-chart of CrI_3 , deposited on top of a 285 nm SiO_2/Si substrate, the respective colors have been extracted from^[305].

Figure 27. Experimental color-chart from 1L-6L of a CrI_3 flake deposited on a 285 nm SiO_2/Si substrate, whose apparent colors have been extracted from^[305].

2.15. PbI_2

Another family of compounds is transition metal halide, whose properties in ultrathin samples are complementary to other 2D groups of materials, i.e., the range of bandgap spans a region not covered by the TMDCs. Lead iodide (PbI_2) belongs to that family, which structure consists of a layer of Pb atoms sandwiched between two layers of I atoms

with van der Waals forces acting as the interlayer interactions, while the intralayer interactions are covalent, shaping a hexagonal crystal structure. This material possesses a shift in its energy bandgap when it is studied in monolayer. The bandgap increases monotonically from a direct value of 2.26 eV in its bulk form, to an indirect bandgap of 2.64 eV in single-layer^[310] according to theoretical calculation. It is consistent with experimental measurements, which yield values from 2.41 eV in bulk to 2.47 eV in monolayer, observing the change of bandgap from direct to indirect^[37]. Thus, the thickness-dependence of the optoelectronic properties is a great asset of this material. Another one is that it shows a higher absorption than others in the UV range^[311–314]. Although a common way to grow this material is in its bulk form, the synthesis of 1D or 2D PbI₂ is mandatory to its later use in devices^[315]. It has been used in a photodetector, observing high responsivity and photogain. In other work, PbI₂-based photodetectors prepared on polyethylene terephthalate have shown superior mechanical stability and durability, also showing a high photoresponsivity and fast response time when compared to others prepared on SiO₂/Si substrate^[312]. In addition, PbI₂ has been used in opto-nonlinear devices^[316]. Other applications of PbI₂ exist apart from the optoelectronic applications, for example nuclear radiation detectors^[317]. Also, intercalation of other

species between its layers is useful to generate new materials with novel properties that can be used in multiple applications^[318].

Figure 28 reports the optical images and color-chart of PbI₂ flakes with thicknesses ranging from 10 nm to 173 nm on 285 nm SiO₂/Si substrate.

Figure 28. (a-j) Optical images of PbI₂ flakes with thickness ranging from 10 nm to 173 nm on 285 nm SiO₂/Si substrate. The bottom panel shows the corresponding color-chart of PbI₂ flakes. Adapted from ^[310]. Copyright (2017), with permission from IOP Publishing.

2.16. MAPbI₃

The organic-inorganic hybrid perovskite CH₃NH₃PbI₃, commonly known as methylammonium lead iodide (MAPbI₃), which structure suffers a phase transition with the temperature, from orthorhombic (10-130 K), tetragonal (190-300 K), to cubic phase (from 350 K)^[319]. It belongs to the family of methylammonium lead halides, which have attracted the interest of use in light-energy conversion devices due to the low-cost production and the easiness of processing. MAPbI₃ is known to be a semiconductor with a direct bandgap of 1.5 eV^[38,39], but with a weakly indirect bandgap of 60 meV below the

direct one. It has been observed that, by applying a hydrostatic pressure from ambient conditions, the direct transition and the radiative efficiency are enhanced^[320]. It has proven to possess superior features when used in perovskite solar cells, such as photo-conversion efficiencies more than 20%^[321]. Although its major drawback is the thermal degradation, several studies have been carried out to improve this behavior to be competitive with commercial solar cells^[322]. Recently, it has been found out that this material, in its tetragonal phase, is also ferroelectric^[323], and it needs to be determined if this property plays a role when used in room-temperature solar cells. It has been demonstrated that, controlling the thickness of thin films MaPbI_3 -based solar cells and other optoelectronic devices is relevant for its performance^[324–326].

Spina M. et al.^[327] have calculated the apparent colors of MAPbI_3 nanowires up to 200 nm as a function of SiO_2/Si and TiO_2/Si substrates. Rods of different colors shown in Figure 29(a) are MaPbI_3 samples on a 280 nm SiO_2/Si substrate. Figures 29(b-c) show the 2D color-charts, in which the vertical axis is the substrate thickness, and the horizontal axis is the MaPbI_3 thickness.

Figure 29. (a) optical image of MAPbI_3 nanowires on 280 nm SiO_2/Si substrate. (b-c) Calculated apparent colors of MAPbI_3 nanowires up to 200 nm on 200-500 nm SiO_2/Si and 50-300 nm TiO_2 substrates, respectively. Adapted from ^[327]. Copyright (2017), with permission from John Wiley and Sons.

2.17. (PEA)₂PbBr₄

Other perovskites have attracted the interest in photovoltaics applications, these are phenethylammonium lead bromide compounds $(C_6H_5C_2H_4NH_3)_2PbBr_4$, usually shortened as $(PEA)_2PbBr_4$, with an optical band gap of 2.9 eV^[40]. These organic-inorganic perovskites are typically prepared using thermal ablation because it is compatible with the deposition of other materials and, in this way, heterostructures such as LEDs and microcavities can be prepared^[328]. During the preparation process, the perovskites are stacked in layers bonded with van der Waals forces, thus they can be easily delaminated with typical methods. Because of the energy bandgaps between the organic and the inorganic sheets, this kind of perovskites behaves as a quantum well, with strong quantum confinement effects. $(PEA)_2PbBr_4$ has also been thoroughly studied in photonics and optoelectronic applications due to ultralow dark current, high detectivity and ON/OFF ratio properties, among others^[40,329].

Figure 30(a) shows optical image of a $(PEA)_2PbBr_4$ flake on 300 nm SiO₂/Si substrate. The color-chart below it shows the apparent color of layers from 1 to 3, 6 and 7L, measured with AFM technique, as shown in Figure 30 (b).

Figure 30. (a) Optical image of $(PEA)_2PbBr_4$ flakes deposited on 300 nm SiO₂/Si substrate with the respective apparent color-chart of this material from 1-3L, 6L and 7L. (b) AFM image of the dashed red box shown in (a), showing the number of layers of the

respective flake. Adapted with permission from ^[330]. Copyright 2021 American Chemical Society.

2.18. BSCCO

$\text{Bi}_2\text{Sr}_2\text{CaCu}_2\text{O}_8$ belongs to copper oxide high-temperature superconductors family, in which some of them possess a layered crystal structure. It is a type-II superconductor with a critical temperature of 105 K ^[331] and shows an intermediate phase of ordinary and superconducting properties at temperatures above that critical temperature. BSCCO needs to be doped with holes by an excess of oxygen to be a superconductor. It was the first high-temperature superconductor that did not have rare-earth compounds^[331].

The most promising application of superconductors is electrical power transport. BSCCO has already been used in the development of a long length transmission voltage cable to operate in an electrical grid, with a total length of 600 m, carrying a current of 2400 A and a voltage of 148 kV^[332]. Furthermore, the thickness-dependence of the superconductivity state has been studied, showing that decreasing the thickness of the sample leads to an increase of the stability of type-II superconductor state against flux jumps^[333]. A flux jump consists of thermomagnetic avalanches that occurs in superconductors, which can destroy the critical state. The flux jump can be induced by a small fluctuation in temperature or by an external magnetic field. A new fabrication of BSCCO process has been developed, in which monolayers of BSCCO can be obtained

with tunable properties and displaying all the fundamental physics of high-temperature superconductivity^[334].

Figure 31 shows several flakes of BSCCO delaminated with the scotch-tape method and placed onto a 271 nm SiO₂/Si substrate. The color-chart below the optical images shows the apparent color of BSCCO flakes with thickness ranging from 10 to 100 nm.

Figure 31. Optical image and color-chart of BSCCO flakes with thickness ranging from 10 nm to 88 nm placed onto a 271 nm SiO₂/Si substrate. Scale bar is 10 μm.

3. Conclusion

2D and thin van der Waals materials have changed our perspective of technology in just a few years. Since the discovery of graphene in 2004, many breakthroughs and studies have been carried out in this sub-field of research, unveiling new physical phenomena. Dealing with this kind of new materials' physical properties and applying them to new functionalities are of a great importance. Several ways to assess the thickness of exfoliated flakes have been developed, but using the thickness dependent apparent colors of flakes, when deposited onto a SiO₂/Si surface, is still one of the most convenient and widespread ones. Here we have presented a review that summarizes the reported thickness dependent apparent color data for a wide range of these new materials. The list of these

materials can be expanded continuously by adding new substrates' thicknesses, other substrates different from SiO₂/Si (such as Si₃N₄/Si, Au/Ti/Si, etc.) and other layered materials. Furthermore, the color-charts that are made from these studies can be useful to implement in machine learning system to make the work of thickness identification even faster and more reliable.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement n° 755655, ERC-StG 2017 project 2D-TOPSENSE), the Spanish Ministry of Economy, Industry and Competitiveness through the grant MAT2017-87134-C2-2-R. SP acknowledges the fellowship PRE2018-084818. H.Z. thanks the support from ITC via the Hong Kong Branch of National Precious Metals Material Engineering Research Center (NPMM), the Research Grants Council of Hong Kong (AoE/P-701/20), the Start-Up Grant (Project No.9380100) and the grants (Project Nos. 9610478, 9680314, 7020013 and 1886921) from the City University of Hong Kong, and the Science Technology and Innovation Committee of Shenzhen Municipality (grant no. JCYJ20200109143412311).

References

- [1] K. S. Novoselov, *Science* **2004**, *306*, 666.
- [2] H. Li, J. Wu, X. Huang, G. Lu, J. Yang, X. Lu, Q. Xiong, H. Zhang, *ACS Nano*

- 2013**, 7, 10344.
- [3] Q. Zhao, S. Puebla, W. Zhang, T. Wang, R. Frisenda, A. Castellanos-Gomez, *Adv. Photonics Res.* **2020**, 1, 2000025.
- [4] S. Puebla, A. Mariscal-Jiménez, R. S. Galán, C. Munuera, A. Castellanos-Gomez, *Nanomaterials* **2020**, 10, 1272.
- [5] P. Ares, F. Zamora, J. Gomez-Herrero, *ACS Photonics* **2017**, 4, 600.
- [6] M. Brotons-Gisbert, J. F. Sánchez-Royo, J. P. Martínez-Pastor, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* **2015**, 354, 453.
- [7] A. Castellanos-Gomez, M. Buscema, R. Molenaar, V. Singh, L. Janssen, H. S. J. van der Zant, G. A. Steele, *2D Mater.* **2014**, 1, 011002.
- [8] Z. E. Hecht; A, *Optics*, Addison Wesley Longman, Amsterdam, **2002**.
- [9] P. Blake, E. W. Hill, A. H. Castro Neto, K. S. Novoselov, D. Jiang, R. Yang, T. J. Booth, A. K. Geim, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2007**, 91, 063124.
- [10] C.-T. Kuo, M. Neumann, K. Balamurugan, H. J. Park, S. Kang, H. W. Shiu, J. H. Kang, B. H. Hong, M. Han, T. W. Noh, J.-G. Park, *Sci. Rep.* **2016**, 6, 074002.
- [11] S. Foteinopoulou, G. C. R. Devarapu, G. S. Subramania, S. Krishna, D. Wasserman, *Nanophotonics* **2019**, 8, 2129.
- [12] K. S. Novoselov, A. K. Geim, S. V. Morozov, D. Jiang, M. I. Katsnelson, I. V. Grigorieva, S. V. Dubonos, A. A. Firsov, *Nature* **2005**, 438, 197.
- [13] X. Yu, T. J. Marks, A. Facchetti, *Nat. Mater.* **2016**, 15, 383.
- [14] Y. Zhao, A. M. Nardes, K. Zhu, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2014**, 104, 213906.
- [15] K. F. Mak, C. Lee, J. Hone, J. Shan, T. F. Heinz, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2010**, 105, 136805.
- [16] D. A. Kunz, J. Erath, D. Kluge, H. Thurn, B. Putz, A. Fery, J. Breu, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2013**, 5, 5851.

- [17] Q. H. Wang, K. Kalantar-Zadeh, A. Kis, J. N. Coleman, M. S. Strano, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2012**, *7*, 699.
- [18] L. Liu, S. B. Kumar, Y. Ouyang, J. Guo, *IEEE Trans. Electron Devices* **2011**, *58*, 3042.
- [19] C. Boix-Constant, S. Mañas-Valero, R. Córdoba, J. J. Baldoví, Á. Rubio, E. Coronado, *ACS Nano* **2021**, *15*, 11898.
- [20] W. Z. Hu, G. Li, J. Yan, H. H. Wen, G. Wu, X. H. Chen, N. L. Wang, *Phys. Rev. B* **2007**, *76*, 045103.
- [21] S. Sugai, K. Murase, *Phys. Rev. B* **1982**, *25*, 2418.
- [22] G. Cassabois, P. Valvin, B. Gil, *Nat. Photonics* **2016**, *10*, 262.
- [23] Y. Sun, S. Luo, X.-G. Zhao, K. Biswas, S.-L. Li, L. Zhang, *Nanoscale* **2018**, *10*, 7991.
- [24] Y. Fan, M. Bauer, L. Kador, K. R. Allakhverdiev, E. Y. Salaev, *J. Appl. Phys.* **2002**, *91*, 1081.
- [25] C. S. Jung, F. Shojaei, K. Park, J. Y. Oh, H. S. Im, D. M. Jang, J. Park, H. S. Kang, *ACS Nano* **2015**, *9*, 9585.
- [26] O. . Hussain, K. . Rao, *Mater. Chem. Phys.* **2003**, *80*, 638.
- [27] S. Das, W. Zhang, M. Demarteau, A. Hoffmann, M. Dubey, A. Roelofs, *Nano Lett.* **2014**, *14*, 5733.
- [28] N. Ehlen, B. V. Senkovskiy, A. V. Fedorov, A. Perucchi, P. Di Pietro, A. Sanna, G. Profeta, L. Petaccia, A. Grüneis, *Phys. Rev. B* **2016**, *94*, 245410.
- [29] A. J. Molina-Mendoza, M. Barawi, R. Biele, E. Flores, J. R. Ares, C. Sánchez, G. Rubio-Bollinger, N. Agraït, R. D'Agosta, I. J. Ferrer, A. Castellanos-Gomez, *Adv. Electron. Mater.* **2015**, *1*, 1500126.
- [30] M. M. Nassary, H. T. Shaban, M. S. El-Sadek, *Mater. Chem. Phys.* **2009**, *113*,

385.

- [31] P. J. S. Foot, J. Suradi, P. A. Lee, *Mater. Res. Bull.* **1980**, *15*, 189.
- [32] C. Lane, J.-X. Zhu, *Phys. Rev. B* **2020**, *102*, 075124.
- [33] R. Kumar, R. N. Jenjeti, M. P. Austeria, S. Sampath, *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2019**, *7*, 324.
- [34] A. J. Molina-Mendoza, E. Giovanelli, W. S. Paz, M. A. Niño, J. O. Island, C. Evangeli, L. Aballe, M. Foerster, H. S. J. van der Zant, G. Rubio-Bollinger, N. Agrait, J. J. Palacios, E. M. Pérez, A. Castellanos-Gomez, *Nat. Commun.* **2017**, *8*, 14409.
- [35] J. F. Dillon, C. E. Olson, *J. Appl. Phys.* **1965**, *36*, 1259.
- [36] Y. Guo, S. Yuan, B. Wang, L. Shi, J. Wang, *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2018**, *6*, 5716.
- [37] M. Zhong, S. Zhang, L. Huang, J. You, Z. Wei, X. Liu, J. Li, *Nanoscale* **2017**, *9*, 3736.
- [38] W. Huang, Y. Liu, S. Yue, L. Zhu, P. Jin, Q. Wu, Y. Zhang, S. Qu, Z. Wang, Y. Chen, *Sci. China Technol. Sci.* **2018**, *61*, 886.
- [39] A. M. A. Leguy, P. Azarhoosh, M. I. Alonso, M. Campoy-Quiles, O. J. Weber, J. Yao, D. Bryant, M. T. Weller, J. Nelson, A. Walsh, M. van Schilfgaarde, P. R. F. Barnes, *Nanoscale* **2016**, *8*, 6317.
- [40] Y. Zhang, Y. Liu, Z. Xu, H. Ye, Q. Li, M. Hu, Z. Yang, S. (Frank) Liu, *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2019**, *7*, 1584.
- [41] N. Hudáková, D. Macko, P. Szabó, P. Samuely, V. Plecháček, *Phys. C Supercond.* **1994**, *235–240*, 1125.
- [42] J. C. Meyer, A. K. Geim, M. I. Katsnelson, K. S. Novoselov, T. J. Booth, S. Roth, *Nature* **2007**, *446*, 60.
- [43] J. A. Wilson, F. J. Di Salvo, S. Mahajan, *Adv. Phys.* **1975**, *24*, 117.

- [44] C. J. Shearer, A. D. Slattery, A. J. Stapleton, J. G. Shapter, C. T. Gibson, *Nanotechnology* **2016**, *27*, 125704.
- [45] Y. Zhu, S. Murali, W. Cai, X. Li, J. W. Suk, J. R. Potts, R. S. Ruoff, *Adv. Mater.* **2010**, *22*, 3906.
- [46] S. Islam, S. S. Z. Ashraf, *Resonance* **2019**, *24*, 445.
- [47] D. R. Cooper, B. D'Anjou, N. Ghattamaneni, B. Harack, M. Hilke, A. Horth, N. Majlis, M. Massicotte, L. Vandsburger, E. Whiteway, V. Yu, *ISRN Condens. Matter Phys.* **2012**, *2012*, 501686.
- [48] A. K. Geim, *Science* **2009**, *324*, 1530.
- [49] K. I. Bolotin, K. J. Sikes, Z. Jiang, M. Klima, G. Fudenberg, J. Hone, P. Kim, H. L. Stormer, *Solid State Commun.* **2008**, *146*, 351.
- [50] S. S. Li, W. R. Thurber, *Solid. State. Electron.* **1977**, *20*, 609.
- [51] C. Lee, X. Wei, J. W. Kysar, J. Hone, *Science* **2008**, *321*, 385.
- [52] F. Bonaccorso, Z. Sun, T. Hasan, A. C. Ferrari, *Nat. Photonics* **2010**, *4*, 611.
- [53] P. Matyba, H. Yamaguchi, G. Eda, M. Chhowalla, L. Edman, N. D. Robinson, *ACS Nano* **2010**, *4*, 637.
- [54] T. Mueller, F. Xia, P. Avouris, *Nat. Photonics* **2010**, *4*, 297.
- [55] J. Guo, J. Li, C. Liu, Y. Yin, W. Wang, Z. Ni, Z. Fu, H. Yu, Y. Xu, Y. Shi, Y. Ma, S. Gao, L. Tong, D. Dai, *Light Sci. Appl.* **2020**, *9*, 29.
- [56] Z. Ullah, G. Witjaksono, I. Nawi, N. Tansu, M. Irfan Khattak, M. Junaid, *Sensors* **2020**, *20*, 1401.
- [57] F. Xia, T. Mueller, Y. Lin, A. Valdes-Garcia, P. Avouris, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2009**, *4*, 839.
- [58] B.-J. Kim, M. A. Mastro, J. Hite, C. R. Eddy, J. Kim, *Opt. Express* **2010**, *18*, 23030.

- [59] X. Li, H. Zhu, K. Wang, A. Cao, J. Wei, C. Li, Y. Jia, Z. Li, X. Li, D. Wu, *Adv. Mater.* **2010**, *22*, 2743.
- [60] D. H. Shin, J. H. Kim, J. H. Kim, C. W. Jang, S. W. Seo, H. S. Lee, S. Kim, S.-H. Choi, *J. Alloys Compd.* **2017**, *715*, 291.
- [61] X. Kong, L. Zhang, B. Liu, H. Gao, Y. Zhang, H. Yan, X. Song, *RSC Adv.* **2019**, *9*, 863.
- [62] N. G. Shang, P. Papakonstantinou, M. McMullan, M. Chu, A. Stamboulis, A. Potenza, S. S. Dhesi, H. Marchetto, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2008**, *18*, 3506.
- [63] S. Alwarappan, A. Erdem, C. Liu, C.-Z. Li, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2009**, *113*, 8853.
- [64] M. Zhou, Y. Zhai, S. Dong, *Anal. Chem.* **2009**, *81*, 5603.
- [65] X. Kang, J. Wang, H. Wu, J. Liu, I. A. Aksay, Y. Lin, *Talanta* **2010**, *81*, 754.
- [66] Y. Ohno, K. Maehashi, Y. Yamashiro, K. Matsumoto, *Nano Lett.* **2009**, *9*, 3318.
- [67] S. Wang, P. K. Ang, Z. Wang, A. L. L. Tang, J. T. L. Thong, K. P. Loh, *Nano Lett.* **2010**, *10*, 92.
- [68] A. M. Abdelkader, N. Karim, C. Vallés, S. Afroj, K. S. Novoselov, S. G. Yeates, *2D Mater.* **2017**, *4*, 035016.
- [69] X. Wang, G. Shi, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2015**, *8*, 790.
- [70] H. Shen, L. Zhang, M. Liu, Z. Zhang, *Theranostics* **2012**, *2*, 283.
- [71] S. Sahu, D. Naik, K. K. Sahoo, N. Sahu, S. Sethi, *Indian J. Public Heal. Res. Dev.* **2019**, *10*, 397.
- [72] K. Zhang, Y. Feng, F. Wang, Z. Yang, J. Wang, *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2017**, *5*, 11992.
- [73] M. F. El-Kady, Y. Shao, R. B. Kaner, *Nat. Rev. Mater.* **2016**, *1*, 16033.
- [74] P. S. Goh, A. F. Ismail, N. Hilal, *Desalination* **2016**, *380*, 100.
- [75] Z. H. Ni, H. M. Wang, J. Kasim, H. M. Fan, T. Yu, Y. H. Wu, Y. P. Feng, Z. X.

- Shen, *Nano Lett.* **2007**, *7*, 2758.
- [76] Y. Li, Y. Kong, J. Peng, C. Yu, Z. Li, P. Li, Y. Liu, C.-F. Gao, R. Wu, *J. Mater.* **2019**, *5*, 413.
- [77] R. M. Sterbentz, K. L. Haley, J. O. Island, *Sci. Rep.* **2021**, *11*, 5808.
- [78] X. Lin, Z. Si, W. Fu, J. Yang, S. Guo, Y. Cao, J. Zhang, X. Wang, P. Liu, K. Jiang, W. Zhao, *Nano Res.* **2018**, *11*, 6316.
- [79] J. Lee, S. Cho, S. Park, H. Bae, M. Noh, B. Kim, C. In, S. Yang, S. Lee, S. Y. Seo, J. Kim, C.-H. Lee, W.-Y. Shim, M.-H. Jo, D. Kim, H. Choi, *J. Phys. D. Appl. Phys.* **2018**, *51*, 11LT03.
- [80] W. Yu, L. Sisi, Y. Haiyan, L. Jie, *RSC Adv.* **2020**, *10*, 15328.
- [81] Z. Luo, P. M. Vora, E. J. Mele, A. T. C. Johnson, J. M. Kikkawa, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2009**, *94*, 111909.
- [82] P. J. S. Foot, J. Suradi, P. A. Lee, *J. Opt.* **1980**, *15*, 189.
- [83] C. Chung, Y.-K. Kim, D. Shin, S.-R. Ryoo, B. H. Hong, D.-H. Min, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2013**, *46*, 2211.
- [84] C. Prasad, Q. Liu, H. Tang, G. Yuvaraja, J. Long, A. Rammohan, G. V. Zyryanov, *J. Mol. Liq.* **2020**, *297*, 111826.
- [85] H. Yang, H. Hu, Y. Wang, T. Yu, *Carbon* **2013**, *52*, 528.
- [86] V. K. Sangwan, M. C. Hersam, *Annu. Rev. Phys. Chem.* **2018**, *69*, 299.
- [87] A. K. Geim, I. V. Grigorieva, *Nature* **2013**, *499*, 419.
- [88] J. A. Wilson, A. D. Yoffe, *Adv. Phys.* **1969**, *18*, 193.
- [89] A. Splendiani, L. Sun, Y. Zhang, T. Li, J. Kim, C.-Y. Chim, G. Galli, F. Wang, *Nano Lett.* **2010**, *10*, 1271.
- [90] Q. Wang, L. Sun, B. Zhang, C. Chen, X. Shen, W. Lu, *Opt. Express* **2016**, *24*, 7151.

- [91] B. Munkhbat, D. G. Baranov, M. Stührenberg, M. Wersäll, A. Bisht, T. Shegai, *ACS Photonics* **2019**, *6*, 139.
- [92] I. Omkaram, Y. K. Hong, S. Kim, in *Two-Dimensional Mater. Photodetector*, InTech, **2018**.
- [93] X. Xia, Z. Zheng, Y. Zhang, X. Zhao, C. Wang, *Sensors Actuators B Chem.* **2014**, *192*, 42.
- [94] A. A. Ramanathan, *IOP Conf. Ser. Mater. Sci. Eng.* **2018**, *305*, 012001.
- [95] J. Theerthagiri, R. A. Senthil, B. Senthilkumar, A. Reddy Polu, J. Madhavan, M. Ashokkumar, *J. Solid State Chem.* **2017**, *252*, 43.
- [96] S. J. McDonnell, R. M. Wallace, *Thin Solid Films* **2016**, *616*, 482.
- [97] Z.-Y. Zhao, Q.-L. Liu, *Catal. Sci. Technol.* **2018**, *8*, 1867.
- [98] W. O. Winer, *Wear* **1967**, *10*, 422.
- [99] T. F. Jaramillo, K. P. Jorgensen, J. Bonde, J. H. Nielsen, S. Horch, I. Chorkendorff, *Science* **2007**, *317*, 100.
- [100] E. Furimsky, *Catal. Rev.* **1980**, *22*, 371.
- [101] S. Tongay, J. Suh, C. Ataca, W. Fan, A. Luce, J. S. Kang, J. Liu, C. Ko, R. Raghunathanan, J. Zhou, F. Ogletree, J. Li, J. C. Grossman, J. Wu, *Sci. Rep.* **2013**, *3*, 2657.
- [102] I. Yakovkin, *Crystals* **2016**, *6*, 143.
- [103] P. Gant, P. Huang, D. Pérez de Lara, D. Guo, R. Frisenda, A. Castellanos-Gomez, *Mater. Today* **2019**, *27*, 8.
- [104] F. Carrascoso, H. Li, R. Frisenda, A. Castellanos-Gomez, *Nano Res.* **2021**, *14*, 1698.
- [105] E. Blundo, M. Felici, T. Yildirim, G. Pettinari, D. Tedeschi, A. Miriametro, B. Liu, W. Ma, Y. Lu, A. Polimeni, *Phys. Rev. Res.* **2020**, *2*, 012024.

- [106] D. Lembke, S. Bertolazzi, A. Kis, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2015**, *48*, 100.
- [107] K. C. J. Lee, Y.-H. Chen, H.-Y. Lin, C.-C. Cheng, P.-Y. Chen, T.-Y. Wu, M.-H. Shih, K.-H. Wei, L.-J. Li, C.-W. Chang, *Sci. Rep.* **2015**, *5*, 16374.
- [108] H. Zhang, Y. Ma, Y. Wan, X. Rong, Z. Xie, W. Wang, L. Dai, *Sci. Rep.* **2015**, *5*, 8440.
- [109] W. Zhao, S. Wang, B. Liu, I. Verzhbitskiy, S. Li, F. Giustiniano, D. Kozawa, K. P. Loh, K. Matsuda, K. Okamoto, R. F. Oulton, G. Eda, *Adv. Mater.* **2016**, *28*, 2709.
- [110] L. Yuan, L. Huang, *Nanoscale* **2015**, *7*, 7402.
- [111] B. Zhu, X. Chen, X. Cui, *Sci. Rep.* **2015**, *5*, 9218.
- [112] N. Peimyoo, J. Shang, C. Cong, X. Shen, X. Wu, E. K. L. Yeow, T. Yu, *ACS Nano* **2013**, *7*, 10985.
- [113] Z. Ye, T. Cao, K. O'Brien, H. Zhu, X. Yin, Y. Wang, S. G. Louie, X. Zhang, *Nature* **2014**, *513*, 214.
- [114] M. Okada, N. Okada, W.-H. Chang, T. Endo, A. Ando, T. Shimizu, T. Kubo, Y. Miyata, T. Irisawa, *Sci. Rep.* **2019**, *9*, 17678.
- [115] H. Zeng, G.-B. Liu, J. Dai, Y. Yan, B. Zhu, R. He, L. Xie, S. Xu, X. Chen, W. Yao, X. Cui, *Sci. Rep.* **2013**, *3*, 1608.
- [116] C.-B. Sun, Y.-W. Zhong, W.-J. Fu, Z.-Q. Zhao, J. Liu, J. Ding, X.-P. Han, Y.-D. Deng, W.-B. Hu, C. Zhong, *Tungsten* **2020**, *2*, 109.
- [117] C. Cong, J. Shang, Y. Wang, T. Yu, *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **2018**, *6*, 1700767.
- [118] A. Łapińska, M. Kuźniewicz, A. P. Gertych, K. Czerniak-Łosiewicz, K. Żerańska-Chudek, A. Wróblewska, M. Świniarski, A. Dużyńska, J. Judek, M. Zdrojek, *Materials (Basel)*. **2020**, *13*, 5315.
- [119] A. Jager-Waldau, M. C. Lux-Steiner, E. Bucher, *Conf. Rec. IEEE Photovolt.*

- Spec. Conf.* **1993**, 597.
- [120] M. K. S. Bin Rafiq, N. Amin, H. F. Alharbi, M. Luqman, A. Ayob, Y. S. Alharthi, nabeel H. Alharthi, B. Bais, M. Akhtaruzzaman, *Sci. Rep.* **2020**, *10*, 771.
- [121] X.-L. Li, W.-P. Han, J.-B. Wu, X.-F. Qiao, J. Zhang, P.-H. Tan, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2017**, *27*, 1604468.
- [122] Y.-C. Lin, T. Björkman, H.-P. Komsa, P.-Y. Teng, C.-H. Yeh, F.-S. Huang, K.-H. Lin, J. Jadczyk, Y.-S. Huang, P.-W. Chiu, A. V. Krasheninnikov, K. Suenaga, *Nat. Commun.* **2015**, *6*, 6736.
- [123] H. Fang, S. Chuang, T. C. Chang, K. Takei, T. Takahashi, A. Javey, *Nano Lett.* **2012**, *12*, 3788.
- [124] H. Yuan, M. S. Bahramy, K. Morimoto, S. Wu, K. Nomura, B. J. Yang, H. Shimotani, R. Suzuki, M. Toh, C. Kloc, X. Xu, R. Arita, N. Nagaosa, Y. Iwasa, *Nat. Phys.* **2013**, *9*, 563.
- [125] A. Eftekhari, *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2017**, *5*, 18299.
- [126] V. Podzorov, M. E. Gershenson, C. Kloc, R. Zeis, E. Bucher, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2004**, *84*, 3301.
- [127] J. K. Huang, J. Pu, C. L. Hsu, M. H. Chiu, Z. Y. Juang, Y. H. Chang, W. H. Chang, Y. Iwasa, T. Takenobu, L. J. Li, *ACS Nano* **2014**, *8*, 923.
- [128] M. R. Müller, A. Gumprich, E. Ecik, K. T. Kallis, F. Winkler, B. Kardynal, I. Petrov, U. Kunze, J. Knoch, *J. Appl. Phys.* **2015**, *118*, 145305.
- [129] C. Ruppert, O. B. Aslan, T. F. Heinz, *Nano Lett.* **2014**, *14*, 6231.
- [130] B. Chen, H. Sahin, A. Suslu, L. Ding, M. I. Bertoni, F. M. Peeters, S. Tongay, *ACS Nano* **2015**, *9*, 5326.
- [131] Y. Ma, Y. Dai, M. Guo, C. Niu, J. Lu, B. Huang, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2011**,

- 13, 15546.
- [132] E. Navarro-Moratalla, J. O. Island, S. Manás-Valero, E. Pinilla-Cienfuegos, A. Castellanos-Gomez, J. Quereda, G. Rubio-Bollinger, L. Chirolli, J. A. Silva-Guillén, N. Agraït, G. A. Steele, F. Guinea, H. S. J. Van Der Zant, E. Coronado, *Nat. Commun.* **2016**, 7, 11043.
- [133] H. Li, G. Lu, Y. Wang, Z. Yin, C. Cong, Q. He, L. Wang, F. Ding, T. Yu, H. Zhang, *Small* **2013**, 9, 1974.
- [134] B. Sipos, A. F. Kusmartseva, A. Akrap, H. Berger, L. Forró, E. Tutiš, *Nat. Mater.* **2008**, 7, 960.
- [135] Y.-F. Cao, K.-M. Cai, L.-J. Li, W.-J. Lu, Y.-P. Sun, K.-Y. Wang, *Chinese Phys. Lett.* **2014**, 31, 077203.
- [136] M. Hossain, Z. Zhao, W. Wen, X. Wang, J. Wu, L. Xie, *Crystals* **2017**, 7, 1.
- [137] G. Grüner, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **1988**, 60, 1129.
- [138] A. H. Thompson, R. F. Gamble, J. F. Revelli, *Solid State Commun.* **1971**, 9, 981.
- [139] S.-H. Lee, J. S. Goh, D. Cho, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2019**, 122, 106404.
- [140] R. Ang, Y. Tanaka, E. Ieki, K. Nakayama, T. Sato, L. J. Li, W. J. Lu, Y. P. Sun, T. Takahashi, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2012**, 109, 176403.
- [141] J. W. Park, G. Y. Cho, J. Lee, H. W. Yeom, *Nat. Commun.* **2019**, 10, 4038.
- [142] Y. Huan, J. Shi, X. Zou, Y. Gong, Z. Zhang, M. Li, L. Zhao, R. Xu, S. Jiang, X. Zhou, M. Hong, C. Xie, H. Li, X. Lang, Q. Zhang, L. Gu, X. Yan, Y. Zhang, *Adv. Mater.* **2018**, 30, 1705916.
- [143] Z. Zeng, C. Tan, X. Huang, S. Bao, H. Zhang, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2014**, 7, 797.
- [144] X. Wang, H. Liu, J. Wu, J. Lin, W. He, H. Wang, X. Shi, K. Suenaga, L. Xie, *Adv. Mater.* **2018**, 30, 1800074.
- [145] L. Zhou, C. Sun, X. Li, L. Tang, W. Guo, L. Luo, M. Zhang, K. S. Teng, F. Qian,

- C. Lu, J. Liang, Y. Yao, S. P. Lau, *Nanoscale Res. Lett.* **2020**, *15*, 20.
- [146] J. P. Tidman, O. Singh, A. E. Curzon, R. F. Frindt, *Philos. Mag.* **1974**, *30*, 1191.
- [147] I. Guillamón, H. Suderow, J. G. Rodrigo, S. Vieira, P. Rodière, L. Cario, E. Navarro-Moratalla, C. Martí-Gastaldo, E. Coronado, *New J. Phys.* **2011**, *13*, 103020.
- [148] A. H. Castro Neto, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2001**, *86*, 4382.
- [149] J. Hall, N. Ehlen, J. Berges, E. van Loon, C. van Efferen, C. Murray, M. Rösner, J. Li, B. V. Senkovskiy, M. Hell, M. Rolf, T. Heider, M. C. Asensio, J. Avila, L. Plucinski, T. Wehling, A. Grüneis, T. Michely, *ACS Nano* **2019**, *13*, 10210.
- [150] L. Fang, Y. Wang, P. Y. Zou, L. Tang, Z. Xu, H. Chen, C. Dong, L. Shan, H. H. Wen, *Phys. Rev. B* **2005**, *72*, 014534.
- [151] F. J. Di Salvo, R. Schwall, T. H. Geballe, F. R. Gamble, J. H. Osiecki, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **1971**, *27*, 310.
- [152] M. Afzali, A. Mostafavi, T. Shamspur, *J. Alloys Compd.* **2020**, *817*, 152742.
- [153] J. Renteria, R. Samnakay, C. Jiang, T. R. Pope, P. Goli, Z. Yan, D. Wickramaratne, T. T. Salguero, A. G. Khitun, R. K. Lake, A. A. Balandin, *J. Appl. Phys.* **2014**, *115*, 034305.
- [154] P. Hajiyev, C. Cong, C. Qiu, T. Yu, *Sci. Rep.* **2013**, *3*, 2593.
- [155] H. J. Park, J. Cha, M. Choi, J. H. Kim, R. Y. Tay, E. H. T. Teo, N. Park, S. Hong, Z. Lee, *Sci. Adv.* **2020**, *6*, eaay4958.
- [156] Y.-N. Xu, W. Y. Ching, *Phys. Rev. B* **1991**, *44*, 7787.
- [157] L. Liu, Y. P. Feng, Z. X. Shen, *Phys. Rev. B* **2003**, *68*, 104102.
- [158] J. Zupan, D. Kolar, *J. Phys. C Solid State Phys.* **1972**, *5*, 3097.
- [159] A. Zunger, A. Katzir, A. Halperin, *Phys. Rev. B* **1976**, *13*, 5560.
- [160] E. Tegeler, N. Kosuch, G. Wiech, A. Faessler, *Phys. Status Solidi* **1979**, *91*, 223.

- [161] R. B. Jacobs-Gedrim, M. Shanmugam, N. Jain, C. A. Durcan, M. T. Murphy, T. M. Murray, R. J. Matyi, R. L. Moore, B. Yu, *ACS Nano* **2014**, *8*, 514.
- [162] J. D. Caldwell, I. Aharonovich, G. Cassabois, J. H. Edgar, B. Gil, D. N. Basov, *Nat. Rev. Mater.* **2019**, *4*, 552.
- [163] C. R. Dean, A. F. Young, I. Meric, C. Lee, L. Wang, S. Sorgenfrei, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, P. Kim, K. L. Shepard, J. Hone, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2010**, *5*, 722.
- [164] A. V. Kretinin, Y. Cao, J. S. Tu, G. L. Yu, R. Jalil, K. S. Novoselov, S. J. Haigh, A. Gholinia, A. Mishchenko, M. Lozada, T. Georgiou, C. R. Woods, F. Withers, P. Blake, G. Eda, A. Wirsig, C. Hucho, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, A. K. Geim, R. V. Gorbachev, *Nano Lett.* **2014**, *14*, 3270.
- [165] A. Woessner, M. B. Lundeberg, Y. Gao, A. Principi, P. Alonso-González, M. Carrega, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, G. Vignale, M. Polini, J. Hone, R. Hillenbrand, F. H. L. Koppens, *Nat. Mater.* **2015**, *14*, 421.
- [166] M. Yankowitz, J. Xue, B. J. LeRoy, *J. Phys. Condens. Matter* **2014**, *26*, 303201.
- [167] M. Yankowitz, Q. Ma, P. Jarillo-Herrero, B. J. LeRoy, *Nat. Rev. Phys.* **2019**, *1*, 112.
- [168] Q. Wang, J. Guo, Z. Ding, D. Qi, J. Jiang, Z. Wang, W. Chen, Y. Xiang, W. Zhang, A. T. S. Wee, *Nano Lett.* **2017**, *17*, 7593.
- [169] A. J. Giles, S. Dai, I. Vurgaftman, T. Hoffman, S. Liu, L. Lindsay, C. T. Ellis, N. Assefa, I. Chatzakis, T. L. Reinecke, J. G. Tischler, M. M. Fogler, J. H. Edgar, D. N. Basov, J. D. Caldwell, *Nat. Mater.* **2018**, *17*, 134.
- [170] J. D. Caldwell, I. Vurgaftman, J. G. Tischler, *Nat. Photonics* **2015**, *9*, 638.
- [171] G. Qiu, Y. Du, A. Charnas, H. Zhou, S. Jin, Z. Luo, D. Y. Zemlyanov, X. Xu, G. J. Cheng, P. D. Ye, *Nano Lett.* **2016**, *16*, 15863.
- [172] Z. Jacob, L. V. Alekseyev, E. Narimanov, *Opt. Express* **2006**, *14*, 8247.

- [173] H. O. Moser, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2011**, *98*, 073501.
- [174] Z. Liu, H. Lee, Y. Xiong, C. Sun, X. Zhang, *Science* **2007**, *315*, 1686.
- [175] C. Liu, J. Zheng, Y. Chen, T. Fryett, A. Majumdar, *Opt. Mater. Express* **2019**, *9*, 384.
- [176] L. J. Martínez, T. Pelini, V. Waselowski, J. R. Maze, B. Gil, G. Cassabo, V. Jacques, *Phys. Rev. B* **2016**, *94*, 121405.
- [177] T. T. Tran, C. Zachreson, A. M. Berhane, K. Bray, R. G. Sandstrom, L. H. Li, T. Taniguchi, K. Watanabe, I. Aharonovich, M. Toth, *Phys. Rev. Appl.* **2016**, *5*, 034005.
- [178] S. Choi, T. T. Tran, C. Elbadawi, C. Lobo, X. Wang, S. Juodkazis, G. Seniutinas, M. Toth, I. Aharonovich, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2016**, *8*, 29642.
- [179] H. Ngoc My Duong, M. A. P. Nguyen, M. Kianinia, T. Ohshima, H. Abe, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, J. H. Edgar, I. Aharonovich, M. Toth, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2018**, *10*, 24886.
- [180] Z.-Q. Xu, C. Elbadawi, T. T. Tran, M. Kianinia, X. Li, D. Liu, T. B. Hoffman, M. Nguyen, S. Kim, J. H. Edgar, X. Wu, L. Song, S. Ali, M. Ford, M. Toth, I. Aharonovich, *Nanoscale* **2018**, *10*, 7957.
- [181] C.-J. Kim, L. Brown, M. W. Graham, R. Hovden, R. W. Havener, P. L. McEuen, D. A. Muller, J. Park, *Nano Lett.* **2013**, *13*, 5660.
- [182] Y. Li, Y. Rao, K. F. Mak, Y. You, S. Wang, C. R. Dean, T. F. Heinz, *Nano Lett.* **2013**, *13*, 3329.
- [183] Q. Zhao, T. Wang, R. Frisenda, A. Castellanos-Gomez, *Adv. Sci.* **2020**, *7*, 2001645.
- [184] Q. Zhao, R. Frisenda, T. Wang, A. Castellanos-Gomez, *Nanoscale* **2019**, *11*, 9845.

- [185] S. Lei, L. Ge, S. Najmaei, A. George, R. Kappera, J. Lou, M. Chhowalla, H. Yamaguchi, G. Gupta, R. Vajtai, A. D. Mohite, P. M. Ajayan, *ACS Nano* **2014**, *8*, 1263.
- [186] G. W. Mudd, S. A. Svatek, T. Ren, A. Patanè, O. Makarovskiy, L. Eaves, P. H. Beton, Z. D. Kovalyuk, G. V. Lashkarev, Z. R. Kudrynskiy, A. I. Dmitriev, *Adv. Mater.* **2013**, *25*, 5714.
- [187] J. Zhou, J. Shi, Q. Zeng, Y. Chen, L. Niu, F. Liu, T. Yu, K. Suenaga, X. Liu, J. Lin, Z. Liu, *2D Mater.* **2018**, *5*, 025019.
- [188] G. Han, Z.-G. Chen, J. Drennan, J. Zou, *Small* **2014**, *10*, 2747.
- [189] M. Wasala, H. I. Sirikumara, Y. Raj Sapkota, S. Hofer, D. Mazumdar, T. Jayasekera, S. Talapatra, *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2017**, *5*, 11214.
- [190] Q. Zhao, W. Wang, F. Carrascoso-Plana, W. Jie, T. Wang, A. Castellanos-Gomez, R. Frisenda, *Mater. Horizons* **2020**, *7*, 252.
- [191] Z. Yang, W. Jie, C.-H. Mak, S. Lin, H. Lin, X. Yang, F. Yan, S. P. Lau, J. Hao, *ACS Nano* **2017**, *11*, 4225.
- [192] S. Lei, F. Wen, L. Ge, S. Najmaei, A. George, Y. Gong, W. Gao, Z. Jin, B. Li, J. Lou, J. Kono, R. Vajtai, P. Ajayan, N. J. Halas, *Nano Lett.* **2015**, *15*, 3048.
- [193] S. R. Tamalampudi, Y.-Y. Lu, R. K. U., R. Sankar, C.-D. Liao, K. M. B., C.-H. Cheng, F. C. Chou, Y.-T. Chen, *Nano Lett.* **2014**, *14*, 2800.
- [194] S. A. Wells, A. Henning, J. T. Gish, V. K. Sangwan, L. J. Lauhon, M. C. Hersam, *Nano Lett.* **2018**, *18*, 7876.
- [195] W. Feng, J.-B. Wu, X. Li, W. Zheng, X. Zhou, K. Xiao, W. Cao, B. Yang, J.-C. Idrobo, L. Basile, W. Tian, P. Tan, P. Hu, *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2015**, *3*, 7022.
- [196] W. Luo, Y. Cao, P. Hu, K. Cai, Q. Feng, F. Yan, T. Yan, X. Zhang, K. Wang, *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **2015**, *3*, 1418.

- [197] H.-W. Yang, H.-F. Hsieh, R.-S. Chen, C.-H. Ho, K.-Y. Lee, L.-C. Chao, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2018**, *10*, 5740.
- [198] G. W. Mudd, S. A. Svatek, L. Hague, O. Makarovskiy, Z. R. Kudrynskiy, C. J. Mellor, P. H. Beton, L. Eaves, K. S. Novoselov, Z. D. Kovalyuk, E. E. Vdovin, A. J. Marsden, N. R. Wilson, A. Patanè, *Adv. Mater.* **2015**, *27*, 3760.
- [199] Q. Zhao, W. Jie, T. Wang, A. Castellanos-Gomez, R. Frisenda, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2020**, *30*, 2001307.
- [200] Z. Chen, J. Biscaras, A. Shukla, *Nanoscale* **2015**, *7*, 5981.
- [201] X. Zhou, J. Cheng, Y. Zhou, T. Cao, H. Hong, Z. Liao, S. Wu, H. Peng, K. Liu, D. Yu, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, *137*, 7994.
- [202] Y. Zhou, Y. Nie, Y. Liu, K. Yan, J. Hong, C. Jin, Y. Zhou, J. Yin, Z. Liu, H. Peng, *ACS Nano* **2014**, *8*, 1485.
- [203] L. Plucinski, R. L. Johnson, B. J. Kowalski, K. Kopalko, B. A. Orlowski, Z. D. Kovalyuk, G. V. Lashkarev, *Phys. Rev. B* **2003**, *68*, 125304.
- [204] S. Zhang, S. Guo, Z. Chen, Y. Wang, H. Gao, J. Gómez-Herrero, P. Ares, F. Zamora, Z. Zhu, H. Zeng, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2018**, *47*, 982.
- [205] P. Hu, Z. Wen, L. Wang, P. Tan, K. Xiao, *ACS Nano* **2012**, *6*, 5988.
- [206] Z. Yin, H. Li, H. Li, L. Jiang, Y. Shi, Y. Sun, G. Lu, Q. Zhang, X. Chen, H. Zhang, *ACS Nano* **2012**, *6*, 74.
- [207] X. Fang, Y. Bando, M. Liao, T. Zhai, U. K. Gautam, L. Li, Y. Koide, D. Golberg, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2010**, *20*, 500.
- [208] B. Chitara, L. S. Panchakarla, S. B. Krupanidhi, C. N. R. Rao, *Adv. Mater.* **2011**, *23*, 5419.
- [209] L. Li, P. Wu, X. Fang, T. Zhai, L. Dai, M. Liao, Y. Koide, H. Wang, Y. Bando, D. Golberg, *Adv. Mater.* **2010**, *22*, 3161.

- [210] L. Karvonen, A. Säynätjoki, S. Mehravar, R. D. Rodriguez, S. Hartmann, D. R. T. Zahn, S. Honkanen, R. A. Norwood, N. Peyghambarian, K. Kieu, H. Lipsanen, J. Riikonen, *Sci. Rep.* **2015**, *5*, 10334.
- [211] Q. Zhao, R. Frisenda, P. Gant, D. Perez de Lara, C. Munuera, M. Garcia-Hernandez, Y. Niu, T. Wang, W. Jie, A. Castellanos-Gomez, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2018**, *28*, 1805304.
- [212] W. Zhang, Q. Zhao, S. Puebla, T. Wang, R. Frisenda, A. Castellanos-Gomez, *Mater. Today Adv.* **2021**, *10*, 100143.
- [213] X. Yu, T. J. Marks, A. Facchetti, *Nat. Mater.* **2016**, *15*, 383.
- [214] L. Cai, C. J. McClellan, A. L. Koh, H. Li, E. Yalon, E. Pop, X. Zheng, *Nano Lett.* **2017**, *17*, 3854.
- [215] S. Balendhran, S. Walia, H. Nili, J. Z. Ou, S. Zhuiykov, R. B. Kaner, S. Sriram, M. Bhaskaran, K. Kalantar-Zadeh, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2013**, *23*, 3952.
- [216] M. F. J. Vos, B. Macco, N. F. W. Thissen, A. A. Bol, W. M. M. (Erwin) Kessels, *J. Vac. Sci. Technol. A Vacuum, Surfaces, Film.* **2016**, *34*, 01A103.
- [217] Y.-C. Tseng, A. U. Mane, J. W. Elam, S. B. Darling, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells* **2012**, *99*, 235.
- [218] A. K. K. Kyaw, X. W. Sun, C. Y. Jiang, G. Q. Lo, D. W. Zhao, D. L. Kwong, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2008**, *93*, 221107.
- [219] C. Battaglia, S. M. de Nicolás, S. De Wolf, X. Yin, M. Zheng, C. Ballif, A. Javey, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2014**, *104*, 113902.
- [220] H. You, Y. Dai, Z. Zhang, D. Ma, *J. Appl. Phys.* **2007**, *101*, 026105.
- [221] W.-J. Shin, J.-Y. Lee, J. C. Kim, T.-H. Yoon, T.-S. Kim, O.-K. Song, *Org. Electron.* **2008**, *9*, 333.
- [222] A. J. Molina-Mendoza, J. L. Lado, J. O. Island, M. A. Niño, L. Aballe, M.

- Foerster, F. Y. Bruno, A. López-Moreno, L. Vaquero-Garzon, H. S. J. van der Zant, G. Rubio-Bollinger, N. Agraït, E. M. Pérez, J. Fernández-Rossier, A. Castellanos-Gomez, *Chem. Mater.* **2016**, 28, 4042.
- [223] K. Kalantar-zadeh, J. Tang, M. Wang, K. L. Wang, A. Shailos, K. Galatsis, R. Kojima, V. Strong, A. Lech, W. Wlodarski, R. B. Kaner, *Nanoscale* **2010**, 2, 429.
- [224] B. W. Reed, D. R. Williams, B. P. Moser, K. J. Koski, *Nano Lett.* **2019**, 19, 4406.
- [225] B. Zheng, Z. Wang, Y. Chen, W. Zhang, X. Li, *2D Mater.* **2018**, 5, 045011.
- [226] W.-B. Zhang, Q. Qu, K. Lai, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2017**, 9, 1702.
- [227] S. Puebla, R. D'Agosta, G. Sanchez-Santolino, R. Frisenda, C. Munuera, A. Castellanos-Gomez, *npj 2D Mater. Appl.* **2021**, 5, 37.
- [228] A. J. Hoffman, L. Alekseyev, S. S. Howard, K. J. Franz, D. Wasserman, V. A. Podolskiy, E. E. Narimanov, D. L. Sivco, C. Gmachl, *Nat. Mater.* **2007**, 6, 946.
- [229] V. A. Podolskiy, E. E. Narimanov, *Phys. Rev. B* **2005**, 71, 201101.
- [230] W. Ma, P. Alonso-González, S. Li, A. Y. Nikitin, J. Yuan, J. Martín-Sánchez, J. Taboada-Gutiérrez, I. Amenabar, P. Li, S. Vélez, C. Tollan, Z. Dai, Y. Zhang, S. Sriram, K. Kalantar-Zadeh, S.-T. Lee, R. Hillenbrand, Q. Bao, *Nature* **2018**, 562, 557.
- [231] Z. Zheng, F. Sun, W. Huang, J. Jiang, R. Zhan, Y. Ke, H. Chen, S. Deng, *Nano Lett.* **2020**, 20, 5301.
- [232] M. Chen, X. Lin, T. H. Dinh, Z. Zheng, J. Shen, Q. Ma, H. Chen, P. Jarillo-Herrero, S. Dai, *Nat. Mater.* **2020**, 19, 1307.
- [233] Z. Zheng, N. Xu, S. L. Oscurato, M. Tamagnone, F. Sun, Y. Jiang, Y. Ke, J. Chen, W. Huang, W. L. Wilson, A. Ambrosio, S. Deng, H. Chen, *Sci. Adv.* **2019**, 5, eaav8690.
- [234] Z. Zheng, J. Chen, Y. Wang, X. Wang, X. Chen, P. Liu, J. Xu, W. Xie, H. Chen,

- S. Deng, N. Xu, *Adv. Mater.* **2018**, *30*, 1705318.
- [235] T. Wang, P. Li, B. Hauer, D. N. Chigrin, T. Taubner, *Nano Lett.* **2013**, *13*, 5051.
- [236] D. N. Basov, M. M. Fogler, F. J. Garcia de Abajo, *Science* **2016**, *354*, aag1992.
- [237] T. Low, A. Chaves, J. D. Caldwell, A. Kumar, N. X. Fang, P. Avouris, T. F. Heinz, F. Guinea, L. Martin-Moreno, F. Koppens, *Nat. Mater.* **2017**, *16*, 182.
- [238] P.-R. Huang, Y. He, C. Cao, Z.-H. Lu, *Sci. Rep.* **2015**, *4*, 7131.
- [239] Y. Takao, A. Morita, *Phys. B+C* **1981**, *105*, 93.
- [240] M. R. M. Atalla, S. J. Koester, in *Device Res. Conf. - Conf. Dig. DRC*, IEEE, **2017**, pp. 1–2.
- [241] W. Choi, M. Y. Cho, A. Konar, J. H. Lee, G.-B. Cha, S. C. Hong, S. Kim, J. Kim, D. Jena, J. Joo, S. Kim, *Adv. Mater.* **2012**, *24*, 5832.
- [242] M. Buscema, D. J. Groenendijk, S. I. Blanter, G. A. Steele, H. S. J. van der Zant, A. Castellanos-Gomez, *Nano Lett.* **2014**, *14*, 3347.
- [243] T. Low, M. Engel, M. Steiner, P. Avouris, *Phys. Rev. B* **2014**, *90*, 081408.
- [244] T. Hong, B. Chamlagain, W. Lin, H.-J. Chuang, M. Pan, Z. Zhou, Y.-Q. Xu, *Nanoscale* **2014**, *6*, 8978.
- [245] X. Lu, L. Sun, P. Jiang, X. Bao, *Adv. Mater.* **2019**, *31*, 1902044.
- [246] J. O. Island, G. A. Steele, H. S. J. van der Zant, A. Castellanos-Gomez, *2D Mater.* **2015**, *2*, 011002.
- [247] L. Viti, A. Politano, K. Zhang, M. S. Vitiello, *Nanoscale* **2019**, *11*, 1995.
- [248] H. Chen, W. Fei, J. Zhou, C. Miao, W. Guo, *Small* **2017**, *13*, 1602336.
- [249] J. O. Island, A. J. Molina-Mendoza, M. Barawi, R. Biele, E. Flores, J. M. Clamagirand, J. R. Ares, C. Sánchez, H. S. J. van der Zant, R. D'Agosta, I. J. Ferrer, A. Castellanos-Gomez, *2D Mater.* **2017**, *4*, 022003.
- [250] S. K. Srivastava, B. N. Avasthi, *J. Mater. Sci.* **1992**, *27*, 3693.

- [251] N. Tripathi, V. Pavelyev, P. Sharma, S. Kumar, A. Rymzhina, P. Mishra, *Mater. Sci. Semicond. Process.* **2021**, *127*, 105699.
- [252] S. Zhao, B. Dong, H. Wang, H. Wang, Y. Zhang, Z. V. Han, H. Zhang, *Nanoscale Adv.* **2020**, *2*, 109.
- [253] J. O. Island, R. Biele, M. Barawi, J. M. Clamagirand, J. R. Ares, C. Sánchez, H. S. J. Van Der Zant, I. J. Ferrer, R. D'Agosta, A. Castellanos-Gomez, *Sci. Rep.* **2016**, *6*, 1.
- [254] I. J. Ferrer, J. R. Ares, J. M. Clamagirand, M. Barawi, C. Sánchez, *Thin Solid Films* **2013**, *535*, 398.
- [255] S. Zhao, B. Dong, H. Wang, H. Wang, Y. Zhang, Z. V. Han, H. Zhang, *Nanoscale Adv.* **2020**, *2*, 109.
- [256] Y. Saeed, A. Kachmar, M. A. Carignano, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2017**, *121*, 1399.
- [257] P. Misse, D. Berthebaud, O. Lebedev, A. Maignan, E. Guilmeau, *Materials (Basel)*. **2015**, *8*, 2514.
- [258] R. Biele, E. Flores, J. R. Ares, C. Sanchez, I. J. Ferrer, G. Rubio-Bollinger, A. Castellanos-Gomez, R. D'Agosta, *Nano Res.* **2018**, *11*, 225.
- [259] A. Lipatov, P. M. Wilson, M. Shekhirev, J. D. Teeter, R. Netusil, A. Sinitskii, *Nanoscale* **2015**, *7*, 12291.
- [260] M. Talib, R. Tabassum, Abid, S. S. Islam, P. Mishra, *ACS Omega* **2019**, *4*, 6180.
- [261] N. Papadopoulos, R. Frisenda, R. Biele, E. Flores, J. R. Ares, C. Sánchez, H. S. J. van der Zant, I. J. Ferrer, R. D'Agosta, A. Castellanos-Gomez, *Nanoscale* **2018**, *10*, 12424.
- [262] H. Mamur, M. R. A. Bhuiyan, F. Korkmaz, M. Nil, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2018**, *82*, 4159.
- [263] L. Yang, Z.-G. Chen, M. Hong, G. Han, J. Zou, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*

- 2015**, 7, 23694.
- [264] Y. Chen, X. Hou, C. Ma, Y. Dou, W. Wu, *Adv. Mater. Sci. Eng.* **2018**, 2018, 1.
- [265] F. J. DiSalvo, *Science* **1999**, 285, 703.
- [266] S. Gupta, *Adv. Mater. Lett.* **2012**, 3, 50.
- [267] P. Srivastava, K. Singh, *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.* **2012**, 110, 523.
- [268] M. Zakeri, M. Allahkarami, G. Kavei, A. Khanmohammadian, M. R. Rahimpour, *J. Mater. Process. Technol.* **2009**, 209, 96.
- [269] C. Vajner, H. Yan, L. Guo, M. Mathews, M. Kuhlman, S. Benefield, S. Ulrich, E. Zolghadr, P. Kung, L. Li, P. T. Araujo, H.-T. Wang, *2D Mater.* **2016**, 3, 021010.
- [270] J.-U. Lee, S. Lee, J. H. Ryoo, S. Kang, T. Y. Kim, P. Kim, C.-H. Park, J.-G. Park, H. Cheong, *Nano Lett.* **2016**, 16, 7433.
- [271] S. Puebla, R. D'Agosta, G. Sanchez-Santolino, R. Frisenda, C. Munuera, A. Castellanos-Gomez, *npj 2D Mater. Appl.* **2021**, 5, 37.
- [272] A. R. Wildes, S. J. Kennedy, T. J. Hicks, *J. Phys. Condens. Matter* **1994**, 6, L335.
- [273] K. Du, X. Wang, Y. Liu, P. Hu, M. I. B. Utama, C. K. Gan, Q. Xiong, C. Kloc, *ACS Nano* **2016**, 10, 1738.
- [274] D. E. Glass, J.-P. Jones, A. V. Shevade, R. V. Bugga, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **2020**, 167, 110512.
- [275] R. Jana, C. Chowdhury, A. Datta, *ChemSusChem* **2020**, 13, 3855.
- [276] R. N. Jenjeti, R. Kumar, M. P. Austeria, S. Sampath, *Sci. Rep.* **2018**, 8, 8586.
- [277] J. Chu, F. Wang, L. Yin, L. Lei, C. Yan, F. Wang, Y. Wen, Z. Wang, C. Jiang, L. Feng, J. Xiong, Y. Li, J. He, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2017**, 27, 1701342.
- [278] C.-T. Kuo, M. Neumann, K. Balamurugan, H. J. Park, S. Kang, H. W. Shiu, J. H. Kang, B. H. Hong, M. Han, T. W. Noh, J.-G. Park, *Sci. Rep.* **2016**, 6, 20904.

- [279] G. Ouvrard, R. Brec, J. Rouxel, *Mater. Res. Bull.* **1985**, *20*, 1181.
- [280] M. Bernasconi, G. L. Marra, G. Benedek, L. Miglio, M. Jouanne, C. Julien, M. Scagliotti, M. Balkanski, *Phys. Rev. B* **1988**, *38*, 12089.
- [281] G. Le Flem, R. Brec, G. Ouvard, A. Louisy, P. Segransan, *J. Phys. Chem. Solids* **1982**, *43*, 455.
- [282] M. Ramos, F. Carrascoso, R. Frisenda, P. Gant, S. Mañas-Valero, D. L. Esteras, J. J. Baldoví, E. Coronado, A. Castellanos-Gomez, M. R. Calvo, *npj 2D Mater. Appl.* **2021**, *5*, 19.
- [283] K. Kim, S. Y. Lim, J. Kim, J.-U. Lee, S. Lee, P. Kim, K. Park, S. Son, C.-H. Park, J.-G. Park, H. Cheong, *2D Mater.* **2019**, *6*, 041001.
- [284] G. Long, H. Henck, M. Gibertini, D. Dumcenco, Z. Wang, T. Taniguchi, K. Watanabe, E. Giannini, A. F. Morpurgo, *Nano Lett.* **2020**, *20*, 2452.
- [285] S. Y. Lim, K. Kim, S. Lee, J.-G. Park, H. Cheong, *Curr. Appl. Phys.* **2021**, *21*, 1.
- [286] C. C. Mayorga-Martinez, Z. Sofer, D. Sedmidubský, Š. Huber, A. Y. S. Eng, M. Pumera, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2017**, *9*, 12563.
- [287] T. A. Shifa, F. Wang, Z. Cheng, P. He, Y. Liu, C. Jiang, Z. Wang, J. He, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2018**, *28*, 1800548.
- [288] S. Lee, K.-Y. Choi, S. Lee, B. H. Park, J.-G. Park, *APL Mater.* **2016**, *4*, 086108.
- [289] X. Li, T. Cao, Q. Niu, J. Shi, J. Feng, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **2013**, *110*, 3738.
- [290] G. Long, T. Zhang, X. Cai, J. Hu, C. Cho, S. Xu, J. Shen, Z. Wu, T. Han, J. Lin, J. Wang, Y. Cai, R. Lortz, Z. Mao, N. Wang, *ACS Nano* **2017**, *11*, 11330.
- [291] Y.-J. Sun, Q.-H. Tan, X.-L. Liu, Y.-F. Gao, J. Zhang, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2019**, *10*, 3087.
- [292] J. Li, K. Yang, L. Du, J. Yi, J. Huang, J. Zhang, Y. He, B. Huang, L. Miao, C. Zhao, S. Wen, *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **2020**, *8*, 2000382.

- [293] E. Makovicky, V. Petricek, M. Dusek, D. Topa, *Am. Mineral.* **2011**, *96*, 1686.
- [294] R. Frisenda, G. Sanchez-Santolino, N. Papadopoulos, J. Urban, M. Baranowski, A. Surrente, D. K. Maude, M. Garcia-Hernandez, H. S. J. van der Zant, P. Plochocka, P. San-Jose, A. Castellanos-Gomez, *Nano Lett.* **2020**, *20*, 1141.
- [295] M. Velický, P. S. Toth, A. M. Rakowski, A. P. Rooney, A. Kozikov, C. R. Woods, A. Mishchenko, L. Fumagalli, J. Yin, V. Zólyomi, T. Georgiou, S. J. Haigh, K. S. Novoselov, R. A. W. Dryfe, *Nat. Commun.* **2017**, *8*, 14410.
- [296] K. Ray, A. E. Yore, T. Mou, S. Jha, K. K. H. Smithe, B. Wang, E. Pop, A. K. M. Newaz, *ACS Nano* **2017**, *11*, 6024.
- [297] A. Barik, L. M. Otto, D. Yoo, J. Jose, T. W. Johnson, S.-H. Oh, *Nano Lett.* **2014**, *14*, 2006.
- [298] L. Wu, Z. Ling, L. Jiang, J. Guo, X. Dai, Y. Xiang, D. Fan, *IEEE Photonics J.* **2016**, *8*, 4801409.
- [299] B. Zeng, Y. Gao, F. J. Bartoli, *Nanoscale* **2015**, *7*, 166.
- [300] S. Gan, Y. Zhao, X. Dai, Y. Xiang, *Results Phys.* **2019**, *13*, 102320.
- [301] P. Gant, F. Ghasemi, D. Maeso, C. Munuera, E. López-Elvira, R. Frisenda, D. P. De Lara, G. Rubio-Bollinger, M. Garcia-Hernandez, A. Castellanos-Gomez, *Beilstein J. Nanotechnol.* **2017**, *8*, 2357.
- [302] L. L. Handy, N. W. Gregory, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1952**, *74*, 891.
- [303] M. A. McGuire, H. Dixit, V. R. Cooper, B. C. Sales, *Chem. Mater.* **2015**, *27*, 612.
- [304] N. Sivadas, S. Okamoto, X. Xu, C. J. Fennie, D. Xiao, *Nano Lett.* **2018**, *18*, 7658.
- [305] B. Huang, G. Clark, E. Navarro-Moratalla, D. R. Klein, R. Cheng, K. L. Seyler, Di. Zhong, E. Schmidgall, M. A. McGuire, D. H. Cobden, W. Yao, D. Xiao, P. Jarillo-Herrero, X. Xu, *Nature* **2017**, *546*, 270.

- [306] L. Webster, J.-A. Yan, *Phys. Rev. B* **2018**, 98, 144411.
- [307] Z. Wu, J. Yu, S. Yuan, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2019**, 21, 7750.
- [308] A. M. León, J. W. González, J. Mejía-López, F. Crasto de Lima, E. Suárez Morell, *2D Mater.* **2020**, 7, 035008.
- [309] B. Huang, G. Clark, D. R. Klein, D. MacNeill, E. Navarro-Moratalla, K. L. Seyler, N. Wilson, M. A. McGuire, D. H. Cobden, D. Xiao, W. Yao, P. Jarillo-Herrero, X. Xu, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2018**, 13, 544.
- [310] R. Frisenda, J. O. Island, J. L. Lado, E. Giovanelli, P. Gant, P. Nagler, S. Bange, J. M. Lupton, C. Schüller, A. J. Molina-Mendoza, L. Aballe, M. Foerster, T. Korn, M. Angel Niño, D. P. de Lara, E. M. Pérez, J. Fernández-Rossier, A. Castellanos-Gomez, *Nanotechnology* **2017**, 28, 455703.
- [311] W. Zheng, Z. Zhang, R. Lin, K. Xu, J. He, F. Huang, *Adv. Electron. Mater.* **2016**, 2, 1600291.
- [312] M. Zhong, L. Huang, H.-X. Deng, X. Wang, B. Li, Z. Wei, J. Li, *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2016**, 4, 6492.
- [313] Y. Wang, L. Gan, J. Chen, R. Yang, T. Zhai, *Sci. Bull.* **2017**, 62, 1654.
- [314] J. P. Ponpon, M. Amann, *Thin Solid Films* **2001**, 394, 276.
- [315] J. Zhang, T. Song, Z. Zhang, K. Ding, F. Huang, B. Sun, *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2015**, 3, 4402.
- [316] H. Maeda, Y. Tanaka, M. Fukutomi, T. Asano, *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.* **1988**, 27, L209.
- [317] C. Manfredotti, R. Murri, A. Quirini, L. Vasanelli, *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.* **1977**, 24, 126.
- [318] N. Preda, L. Mihut, M. Baibarac, I. Baltog, S. Lefrant, *J. Phys. Condens. Matter* **2006**, 18, 8899.

- [319] P. S. Whitfield, N. Herron, W. E. Guise, K. Page, Y. Q. Cheng, I. Milas, M. K. Crawford, *Sci. Rep.* **2016**, *6*, 35685.
- [320] T. Wang, B. Daiber, J. M. Frost, S. A. Mann, E. C. Garnett, A. Walsh, B. Ehrler, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2017**, *10*, 509.
- [321] Z. Chen, B. Turedi, A. Y. Alsalloum, C. Yang, X. Zheng, I. Gereige, A. AlSaggaf, O. F. Mohammed, O. M. Bakr, *ACS Energy Lett.* **2019**, *4*, 1258.
- [322] T. T. Ava, A. Al Mamun, S. Marsillac, G. Namkoong, *Appl. Sci.* **2019**, *9*, 188.
- [323] P. S. Whitfield, N. Herron, W. E. Guise, K. Page, Y. Q. Cheng, I. Milas, M. K. Crawford, *Sci. Rep.* **2016**, *6*, 35685.
- [324] C. Wang, C. Zhang, S. Tong, J. Shen, C. Wang, Y. Li, S. Xiao, J. He, J. Zhang, Y. Gao, J. Yang, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2017**, *121*, 6575.
- [325] W. E. I. Sha, X. Ren, L. Chen, W. C. H. Choy, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2015**, *106*, 221104.
- [326] L. Chen, J. Cai, J. Li, S. P. Feng, G. Wei, W. Di Li, *Org. Electron.* **2019**, *71*, 284.
- [327] M. Spina, C. Grimaldi, B. Náfrádi, L. Forró, E. Horváth, *Phys. status solidi* **2016**, *213*, 2017.
- [328] S. Zhang, P. Audebert, Y. Wei, A. Al Choueiry, G. Lanty, A. Bréhier, L. Galmiche, G. Clavier, C. Boissière, J.-S. Lauret, E. Deleporte, *Materials (Basel)*. **2010**, *3*, 3385.
- [329] X. Gao, X. Shen, D. Xue, X. Li, P. Lu, M. Lu, C. Li, W. W. Yu, X. Bai, *Mater. Chem. Front.* **2021**, *5*, 937.
- [330] Y. Wang, F. Song, Y. Yuan, J. Dang, X. Xie, S. Sun, S. Yan, Y. Hou, Z. Lou, X. Xu, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2021**, *12*, 2133.
- [331] H. Maeda, Y. Tanaka, M. Fukutomi, T. Asano, *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.* **1988**, *27*, L209.

- [332] J. F. Maguire, F. Schmidt, F. Hamber, T. E. Welsh, *IEEE Trans. Applied Supercond.* **2005**, *15*, 1787.
- [333] A. Nabałek, M. Niewczas, *Phys. C Supercond.* **2006**, *436*, 43.
- [334] Y. Yu, L. Ma, P. Cai, R. Zhong, C. Ye, J. Shen, G. D. Gu, X. H. Chen, Y. Zhang, *Nature* **2019**, *575*, 156.